

**Master Of Business Administration in International Health Management
(MBA IHM)**

**Gender equity in health financing towards
achieving universal health coverage: What
does it take to successfully address
inequities that affect women's access to
healthcare?**

A thesis submitted to the Swiss Tropical and Public Health Institute, University
of Basel, in partial fulfilment of the MBA Programme in International Health
Management

Marie Beille

December 2024

Table of contents

Abstract	2
Introduction	3
Background.....	3
Objective.....	7
Methods	9
1. Scope clarification and CMO configuration	9
2. Literature search.....	14
3. Selection of relevant articles	15
4. Data extraction.....	19
5. Evidence synthesis	21
Results	22
UHC reforms and publicly-funded schemes.....	23
Other insurance schemes	35
Demand-side financing mechanisms and SRH services	42
Discussion	53
Conclusions	65
References	69

Abstract

Background and objective

Health financing is recognised as the most critical health system component to achieve UHC. UHC is built on the principle of equity, yet UHC and health financing strategies are still gender-blind and perpetuate pervasive gender inequities. This thesis is a realist review that assesses how to address gender inequities in health financing that affect women's ability to access and utilise healthcare services according to their needs, compared to men. It aims to define the conditions for the success of policies and programmes in addressing those inequities.

Methods

The thesis is theory-driven and follows the standard realist review approach. Three theories were formulated. An initial search using PubMed was completed to identify policies across geographies and intervention types for which there is evidence of successful impact on gender inequities. Additional literature was identified to test theories across certain geographies and intervention types.

Results and conclusions

The theories were overall confirmed and enriched. Policies and programmes proactively integrating gender perspectives and addressing intersectional factors are more likely to improve women's ability to utilise a financial protection scheme and to receive quality care. Health financing programmes complemented with investments and interventions to improve the capacity and quality of healthcare delivery are more likely to benefit women. UHC schemes should carefully consider the gender implications of enrolment criteria and methods in the design and execution of their benefit packages. Across diverse contexts, social participation and community engagement are critical success factors to contribute to addressing gendered social and cultural barriers and help sustain political will and government commitment towards gender-equitable health financing programmes and UHC reforms.

Introduction

Background

Health financing is one of the core components (“building block”) of health systems (World Health Organization 2010b) and recognised as the most critical to achieve universal health coverage (UHC) (World Health Organization 2005, 2010c). UHC is fundamental to keep the promise to “leave no one behind” of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) adopted by all nations in the world in 2015 (UN General Assembly 2019) and means that all people can access all the quality health services they need without suffering financial hardship (World Health Organization 2010c). UHC is built on the principle of equity and requires a “progressive universalism” approach to be achieved, which entails putting the health needs and the financial protection of the poorest and most vulnerable first (Gwatkin and Ergo 2011; Jamison et al. 2013; UN General Assembly 2019). However, today, indicators show that large inequalities across different population groups persist, as most countries have so far failed to deliver equitable health financing policies (Third Annual UHC Financing Forum 2018) and to progress towards reducing catastrophic out of pocket (OOP) payments or improving service coverage overall (World Health Organization and World Bank 2023).

One large, vulnerable group which is recognised as having higher needs while facing persistent inequalities is women. The WHO defines gender equality as “equal chances or opportunities for women and men to access and control social, economic and political resources within families, communities and society at large, including protection under the law (such as health services, education and voting rights)”, while gender equity recognises that differential treatment is needed to ensure fairness and justice in the distribution of benefits and responsibilities between women and men and achieve equality of opportunities (World Health Organization 2010a). Biological differences between the sexes mean that women and men have different health needs (Criado-Perez 2019; Langer et al. 2015; Sen et al. 2007). For health research, it is important to differentiate the terms sex and gender: sex refers to the biological characteristics

that define being female or male, whereas gender refers to socially constructed roles and norms for women and men (Kaufman et al. 2023). These impact the lives of women and men in multiple ways - access to education and schooling, types of work, expectations in the home regarding child bearing, care giving, housework etc. Sex disparities in health needs consequently call for gender equity strategies, as women and men require differential treatment by health policies, including health financing and UHC programmes to ensure they have equality of opportunities to access the health services they need (PAHO 2021).

Extensive research demonstrates the significant, negative impact that gender has on health, beyond biology alone, as a determinant of health, but also as women are disproportionately affected by other social determinants of health such as race or ethnicity, age, ability, poverty and economic vulnerability, social status or access to education (Langer et al. 2015; Sen et al. 2007; Heise, L. et al. 2019). This interaction of gender with other dimensions of inequality is referred to as intersectionality. Worldwide, social and cultural norms create gender-based differences in health status, health-seeking behaviour and access to care, which are reinforced by gender-biased health research and health systems (Heise, L. et al. 2019; Criado-Perez 2019). Policies and programmes ignoring gender inequalities are defined as “gender-blind”. Those that acknowledge gender inequalities but will not necessarily address them are defined as “gender-sensitive” and those that actively address women’s (or men’s) specific needs are “gender-specific”. “Gender-transformative” reforms address the underlying causes of gender inequities and include strategies to foster progressive change (World Health Organization 2010a).

UHC and health financing strategies are still found to be gender-blind today (Percival et al. 2014; Percival et al. 2018; UHC2030 2020). Health financing policies that claim to be gender-neutral and to affect both sexes equally perpetuate existing inequalities and are in fact gender-blind (Moradkhvaj and Saikia 2019). There is little to no gender-disaggregated data available to understand status and progress (PAHO 2021). Yet, a large body of evidence has shown that women are more likely to be excluded from UHC than men (Ravindran

2012) and UHC and health financing reforms can not only fail to improve gender equality, they may also even exacerbate gender inequities (Witter et al. 2017).

For example, many studies have shown that across all continents and economies, women's out-of-pocket payments are systematically higher than men's and prevent them more than men from using essential services (World Health Organization 2010a). Men's healthcare costs are also more likely to be financed through various coping strategies than that of women, especially within resource-constrained households and communities (Moradvaj and Saikia 2019; Azad et al. 2020). Even when financial barriers have seemingly been removed by a UHC scheme or other health financing mechanisms, women remain disproportionately exposed to frequent and prohibitive out-of-pocket payments arising from informal payments, non-medical expenditure or additional care costs, compared to men (PAHO 2021; Ravindran and Govender 2020; Nanda P. 2002; Onah and Govender 2014; Vijayasingham et al. 2020). This is mainly due to non-coverage or limits on coverage where women have greater health needs, notably in the context of sexual and reproductive health (SRH) and access to abortion (Witter et al. 2017), but also implies that even in countries that have made significant progress towards UHC, the financing systems in place may be inequitable.

Employment-based financing mechanisms favour men because worldwide, less women are formally employed, and when they are, they are paid less than men (Vijayasingham et al. 2020). Yet many UHC systems have relied on such mechanisms, which include payroll-based social insurance contributions or mandatory or semi-mandatory provision of health insurance by employers, despite evidence that they lead to inequality (Yazbeck et al. 2020). Gender inequalities are also found in the enrolment and utilization of publicly funded schemes (Cerceau 2012; PAHO 2021; RamPrakash and Lingam 2021). XX

Those persisting and pervasive inequalities translate into negative health outcomes for women and girls, but also for men (Sen et al. 2007). Women experience a longer life expectancy than men in all countries in the world, but a higher morbidity, and women's health outcomes are now at a growing

disadvantage compared to men's (Kindig and Cheng 2013; Freedman et al. 2016; Baum et al. 2021). Tackling such gender inequalities represent not only one of the most powerful ways to reduce health inequities, but also a very large sustainable development opportunity (Langer et al., 2015; World Economic Forum and McKinsey Health Institute, 2024).

Well-designed UHC programs have shown positive impacts on women's access to needed health services, such as Mexico or Thailand (Quick et al. 2014), which have been relatively well researched. However, most of the evidence on health financing reforms that have somehow progressed towards improving women's financial protection and equitable access to healthcare focus on gender-specific interventions for sexual and reproductive health (SRH), notably maternal health, such as removal of user fees or conditional cash transfers, and little in the context of UHC (Witter et al. 2017). While access to SRH is essential for gender equity in health and more broadly for sustainable development and progress towards UHC and SHR, both SDGs, are mutually reinforcing (Starrs et al. 2018; Ravindran and Govender 2020), women's health needs and subsequent research are frequently reduced to those of their reproductive role (PAHO 2021).

As outlined, there is aggregated evidence of the challenges, root causes and the large remaining evidence gaps of gender implications of UHC and health financing mechanisms. Building on this, a consequent body of literature calls for action and proposes directions for change, highlighting the importance "gender mainstreaming", defined as paying explicit attention to gender and its intersectionality with other social determinants in legislation, policies and programmes. This entails integrating comprehensive gender equity strategies from the start in UHC and health financing reforms, across the multiple health systems blocks (Sen et al. 2021; World Health Organization 2010a). However, there appears to be far less research on the solutions, and studies that do show a positive impact of policies and programmes on gender inequities do not deliver explanatory evidence of what works, why and how, so that they can be leveraged by policy makers and other stakeholders who look for the best way to tailor

solutions to their local contexts (Ravindran and Govender 2020; Heymann et al. 2019).

This thesis will therefore build from that and focus on reviewing what has made policies and interventions that have taken gender-equitable approaches to health financing effective and what are the factors that contributed to their effectiveness.

Objective

The thesis assesses how to address gender inequities in health financing that affect women's ability to access and utilise healthcare services according to their needs, compared to men. It aims to address the following question: what does it take to successfully address gender inequities in health financing towards achieving universal health coverage? It aims to define the conditions for the success of policies and programmes in addressing those inequities. Success is defined and assessed in the context of UHC, as progress towards equal opportunities for women and men to access the health services they need without suffering financial hardship. It intends to inform policy makers, health financing and gender experts as well as international development and private sector partners in the design and implementation of health financing strategies.

It is recognised that progress towards more equitable health financing is fundamental to achieve UHC and other SDG-related goals such as achieving poverty elimination and gender equality (The World Bank 2019; Third Annual UHC Financing Forum 2018). It is also recognised that intersectionality as well as mainstreaming gender across all health system blocks are critical to advance towards gender-equitable health financing and UHC (Sen et al. 2021). It is, however, also acknowledged that health financing policymakers have little guidance on what represents a "best practice" as they face, especially where resources are scarce, difficult trade-offs when looking to improve equity between different population groups while also aiming to achieve other health financing, UHC or development objectives such as quality and efficiency of care or economic growth (Third Annual UHC Financing Forum 2018). Few studies have comprehensively analysed the factors behind the success of countries and interventions that progressed towards gender-equitable health financing.

There is therefore an opportunity to consolidate and analyse learnings from countries' experiences and progress over the past twenty years as governments, in the context of the MDGs and now the SDGs, committed to equitable health financing strategies to achieve UHC and gender equality.

Methods

A realist review was chosen as the literature review methodology. Realist reviews are theory-driven and used to assess interventions taking into consideration their implementation contexts. Rather than asking, “does the intervention work?”, realist reviews ask “what is it about this intervention that works, for whom, under what circumstances, and how?” (Jagosh 2019). Such reviews aim to identify the hidden causal mechanisms and contextual determinants behind an intervention’s outcomes. This causal explanation is hypothesised using a context-mechanism-outcome (CMO) configuration (Pawson et al. 2005). The review then assesses the integrity of those theories.

This methodology aligns very closely with the thesis’ objectives. As discussed, gender inequalities in health intersect with many other social determinants of health and arise from the differences in the way societies and cultures value men and women. Studies that applied a gender lens to assess health financing interventions have highlighted previously unseen factors causing, perpetuating or exacerbating gender inequities (PAHO 2021; Morgan et al. 2018), demonstrating the importance of understanding underlying causal effects.

The thesis studies interventions that aimed to improve equity in the three functions of a health financing system: revenue raising, fund pooling and purchasing (Kutzin et al. 2010), and have improved gender inequities in health financing, by providing an evidence-based review of *how* they have, under which circumstances, for whom, to inform the successful development of health financing strategies tailored to any local context. Assessing and taking context and circumstances into consideration is critical to address the thesis’ research question.

The review follows the standard approach to realist reviews, comprised of five overlapping and iterative steps (Pawson et al. 2005; Rycroft-Malone et al. 2012).

1. Scope clarification and CMO configuration

Building from the initial literature review already performed, specific objectives to address the thesis’ research question can be articulated in the CMO (context-

mechanism-outcome) configuration. The different steps of the review process led to test the theories' integrity, and to support, modify or refine them.

The initial CMO statements are defined based on two selected studies that have looked at several countries' experience with gender implications of health financing strategies for UHC and subsequently formulated theories and policy recommendations: Ravindran 2012 "Universal access: making health systems work for women" and Witter et al. 2017 "Minding the gaps: health financing, universal health coverage and gender". Those studies were chosen because they provide a good overview of the existing literature, findings and conclusions on the thesis's topic – focusing more on challenges and barriers rather than solutions and successful use cases, as was discussed in most of the literature on the topic. The papers and their authors are considered key references in the field, frequently quoted by additional research. Three initial theories were therefore tested:

CMO 1: For health financing policies and programmes (C), proactively and explicitly including gender perspectives from the start and adopt intersectional approaches (M) is essential to tackle inequities hindering progress towards UHC (O).

Witter et al.'s study summarises the evidence on the gendered effects of policies across the three health financing functions: revenue collection and pooling for healthcare and health purchasing. It provides several examples of how more women, compared to men, are prevented from benefiting from health financing programmes meant to improve various population segments' financial protection, ranging from removal of user fees, private and voluntary insurance schemes, social health insurance reforms to the design and purchasing of benefit packages. The causes of those inequalities are well-known gender biases at societal and household levels that make women disproportionately affected by other social determinants of health such as race or ethnicity, age, religion or caste, limit their access to and control over financial resources and increase their risk of receiving poor or even harmful care. Ravindran's paper, which looks at gender inequities across the three dimensions of UHC (the size of the population covered, the

range of services covered, and the proportion of the costs covered (World Health Organization 2010c)), reaches similar conclusions. Both papers bring out, on the other hand, cases where health financing reforms have positively impacted women's access to healthcare because they proactively and explicitly addressed women's specific health needs and adopted measures to tackle underlying political and social determinants affecting access for vulnerable groups such as adolescents or poor indigenous women, notably Mexico and Thailand's UHC reforms. They both find that health financing reforms should therefore pay explicit attention to gender and its intersectionality with other social determinants if they want to improve equity and gender balance. If they don't, they are in fact likely to exacerbate gender inequity and defeat the overarching UHC purpose.

This leads to the theory that gender and its intersectionality with other determinants should be proactively and explicitly considered, from the start, for any changes in health financing functions to successfully expand UHC. As also argued by (Sen et al. 2021), such consideration requires changes across the other health system blocks, such as: ensuring that service provision is designed to reduce women's specific access barriers, that the workforce is trained adequately to provide ethical and equitable care, that information systems collect sex-disaggregated data and that gender-transformative governance systems are put in place, integrating the representation of women in decision-making processes. This theory implies that political will and determination is the pivotal success factor and that governments should prioritise securing the means – technical, human and financial – to implement the needed health system changes.

CMO 2: UHC reforms (C) need to apply a gender perspective when defining enrolment criteria, revenue collection and benefit packages (M) to ensure they do not exclude large groups of women based on their age and different health needs, their income level, whether they work in the informal sector or in a rural area (O).

The starting point of Witter et al.'s paper is a reflection on the question raised in a webinar in 2015 of why a focus on gender is needed "given that a well-

functioning system moving towards UHC will automatically be equitable and gender balanced". As discussed in the introduction, evidence clearly shows that progressive universalism applied as a general concept is not sufficient to ensure movements towards UHC will achieve equity, because, as Witter et al. argues, equity is predominantly conceptualised in relation to income and geography, while gender inequities and their intersectionality with other social determinants are largely underestimated. Both papers discuss evidence that not all UHC reforms are gender-equitable and that the most equitable form of revenue raising and pooling mechanisms are compulsory public financing schemes, and especially tax-based schemes. As previously mentioned, compulsory employment-based financing schemes disproportionately benefit men because much less women are formally employed than men and when they are, they are paid less than men. However, relying solely on general tax revenue is challenging for many low and middle-income economies, and countries like Mexico or Thailand that have achieved rapid progress towards UHC and tackling financial barriers for the economically vulnerable, did so through a combination of employment-based social health insurance and tax revenue, which financially covers the economically vulnerable.

Both Ravindran and Witter et al.'s papers discuss the importance of enrolment criteria and methods of UHC schemes. For example, experience from the RSBY scheme in India, which set a limit of 5 members per household has shown that women were more likely to be excluded even from publicly financed schemes; the PM-JAY scheme, which replaced RSBY, no longer caps enrolment within households, as is also the case in Mexico and Thailand.

The papers also emphasize the need to define benefit packages with a gender perspective, by acknowledging the differences in health needs between women and men across a broad range of conditions beyond maternal health and SRH, such as non-communicable diseases or mental health. Adolescent girls and elderly women are often excluded from coverage because of the almost exclusive focus on maternal and reproductive health in essential service packages. Even then, coverage of SRH services is found to be rarely comprehensive.

This leads to the theory that UHC schemes, whether tax- or employment-based, need to apply a gender perspective when defining enrolment criteria, revenue collection and benefit packages to ensure they do not exclude large groups of women. This implies that policymakers acknowledge that pro-poor reforms that consider certain segments such as the informal sector or rural population will continue to exclude a large proportion of the vulnerable population, unless they explicitly pay attention to gender too.

CMO 3: Gender-specific interventions, such as removal of user fees and conditional cash-transfers for maternal and sexual and reproductive health services (C) that are combined with measures to tackle underlying cultural, political and social determinants that undermine women and girls' access to care (M) are more likely to reach their intended outcomes (O).

As previously outlined, access to comprehensive, quality SRH is fundamental for UHC, gender equity and sustainable development. It is a target for both SDG 3 “good health and well-being” and SDG 5 “gender equality” (UN General Assembly 2015). Maternal health was already one of the Millennium Development Goals (2000-2015, Millennium Development Goals 2024) and is now also a specific target within SDG 3. This means that many of the efforts towards improving financial protection for women and the subsequent evidence on their impact have been focused on SRH and maternal health.

Both Ravindran and Witter et al.'s papers collect evidence on several health financing reforms specifically aimed at improving women's access to SRH, with a focus on maternal health, such as demand-side financing mechanisms (DSF) like vouchers or conditional cash transfers (CCTs) or removal of user fees. In a prior paper, Witter defined DSF as “actions which transfer resources to households on condition that they utilize specific services” (Witter and Somanathan 2012). Because they intentionally target women and focus on certain health needs, the interventions discussed here are gender-specific. Both papers find that in many contexts, those health financing mechanisms did improve utilisation, access and in some instances, key indicators. Yet, their impact and sustainability are too often limited because they do not address the

root causes affecting some women's ability to pay for and access healthcare services. Consequently, they fail to reach targeted women or fail to provide an adequate financial protection.

Both papers discuss how CCTs in programs like India's Muthulakshmi Reddy Maternity Benefit Scheme in Tamil Nadu or Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) improved institutional deliveries, but many marginalized women, despite being the schemes' primary targets, were still excluded due to social and administrative barriers, such as lacking the necessary documents or not satisfying eligibility criteria because they already had two live births, despite fertility levels being considerably higher among the poorest and uneducated women. Ravindran also mentions that the cash incentive in CCTs is often insufficient to protect from catastrophic expenditure, which may have perverse consequences if vulnerable women are incentivised to use facilities in which they incur more costs than they can afford. Witter et al. collects evidence that DSF mechanisms should also be combined with efforts to address intra-households' power relations and acceptability of care, for example by involving men. The paper also highlights the need to pair demand-side interventions with supply-side efforts to improve care quality. Evidence shows that increased demand from DSF schemes has strained facilities and healthcare workers, leading to questionable practices that perpetuate risks and barriers for women seeking care.

This leads to the theory that gender-specific health financing interventions are more likely to reach their intended outcomes if they are combined with non-financial measures to tackle underlying determinants that undermine women and girls' access to care. As policy-makers are encouraged to adopt gender-transformative universal access reforms that comprehensively address women's health needs and gender inequities, there is therefore an interest to assess what makes gender-specific health financing interventions sustainable and impactful, and in which contexts do they remain pertinent options.

2. Literature search

Literature search in realist review is expected to be iterative and use evolving search strategies, and thus should not rely on an initial finite set of papers, as it

seeks to explore and contextualize interventions in multiple settings. (Pawson et al. 2005). While the preliminary literature review highlighted the dearth of evidence on gender implications of existing health financing policies and programmes, it helped identify an initial range of policy and programme types to study, which formed, as presented in the background section, the basis of the initial theories.

The initial search strategy was therefore meant to further refine and confirm the clusters of policies and interventions the review should then focus on the test the theories. It was built after a consultation with an information specialist of the University of Basel and was performed on 25 July 2024 using PubMed as well as Scopus for citation searching (see figure 1; table 1; table 2 in Appendix).

3. Selection of relevant articles

In a realist review, the selection process looks at the data and its ability to contribute to theory building and testing rather than applying strict selection and exclusion criteria to studies. Articles were therefore appraised based on the three proposed criteria for realist reviews: their relevance (is the data relevant to the theories?), richness (can it meaningfully contribute to theory testing or building?) and rigour (is it credible and trustworthy?) (Dada et al. 2023).

Relevance

To determine whether the data is relevant to theory building and/or testing, documents identified during the literature search were first assessed with the following inclusion and exclusion criteria:

Inclusion criteria:

- Documents presenting policies or programmes that address at least one health financing function, AND
- Documents that provide evidence of a policy or programme's impact on gender inequities or inequalities in health financing. Evidence includes at a minimum gender disaggregated data from health financing indicators such as coverage rate, utilisation and catastrophic or impoverishing OOP,

and ideally, disaggregated data about health outcomes and health service delivery across determinants such as gender, age, socioeconomic status.

Exclusion criteria:

- Documents older than the year 2000, as concepts and strategies associated to gender mainstreaming and global health mobilization towards gender equality started to actively emerge then, OR
- Documents in a language other than English, OR
- Documents that do not directly address any health financing function or mechanism, OR
- Documents that do not directly address gender inequities or inequalities.

While many documents were simply excluded during the initial search, some of them were retained for future consideration depending on theory testing and further development. This includes documents that addressed inequities in health financing but not specifically gender, documents that addressed gender inequities in health and access to healthcare, but not specifically in health financing, or documents that addressed gender inequities in health financing but merely provided evidence of such inequities rather than of interventions that could address them.

Richness

Relevant documents were then appraised for their richness, to answer the following question: can they meaningfully contribute to theory development or testing? Richness was considered high if the document provided a rich description of the intervention context, strategy, implementation process or mechanism, providing information on causal pathways and contributing to explaining how it works. In that case, the document was further selected. Richness was considered low if the document provided little to no information on the intervention that could contribute to refining the theories or developing new ones. Some documents with low richness were excluded at this stage, but many were retained for future consideration. This includes for example documents that

provided little to no detail on interventions, but provided references to documents that could.

Rigour

The documents' rigour was then considered, to assess whether they could make a credible contribution to test the theories. The credibility and trustworthiness of the source and the methods used for analysis were evaluated based on the following proposed questions (Dada et al. 2023): Is this data likely to be biased? Is it dealt with critically? Is it from a real-world example or theoretical speculation? Is it safe to generalise from this data?

Figure 1 Initial search: Selection of studies

Table 1 Search strategy

<p>Initial search (Table 2 in appendix)</p>	<p>Date: 25 July 2024</p> <p>1. PubMed searches</p> <p>a. (equity OR inequity OR equality) AND (gender) AND (universal-health-coverage OR health-financ*)</p> <p>b. Merging equity and gender concepts for more specificity: (gender-equity OR gender-inequity OR gender-equality OR gender-neutral OR gender-mainstreaming OR gender-specific) AND (health-financ* OR universal-health-coverage OR universal-coverage)</p> <p>2. Forward and backward citation searching for 3 key articles identified during preliminary literature review using Scopus</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forward and backward citation searching for (Witter et al. 2017) • Forward and backward citation searching for (Ravindran 2012) • Backward citation searching for (Remme et al. 2020). <p>Studies included in review: n=22</p>
<p>Iterative searches</p>	<p>Subsequent searches on following focus areas identify additional evidence eligible to refine, refute, or confirm the initial theories. Key words used for those searches, in addition to those mentioned, included country names or specific programmes, such as “PM-JAY” or “ACA”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Countries: India, Thailand, Mexico, Indonesia • DSF mechanisms & Maternal/SRH health • CBHI, especially Rwanda • Private health insurance especially the USA <p>Methods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrieval of articles from preliminary search • Retrieval of articles excluded during the appraisal phase • WHO, World Bank databases, Google • Experts contacted to (key references in this field, authored foundational work on the topic many references selected) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sundari Ravindran (call scheduled missed, could not follow-up) ○ Sophie Witter (completed call on 9 October 2024) ○ Veloshnee Govender (completed call on 23 October 2024) ○ Manuela Di Allegri (completed call on 24 October 2024) <p>Additional studies included for evidence synthesis (Result section): n=50</p>

4. Data extraction

To extract and analyse data relevant to the tested theories, PAHO's proposed model for gender equality framework and indicators in the context of universal health and the Sustainable Development Goals (Pan American Health Organization 2019) was used (Figure 2). PAHO's framework is an adaptation of the model developed for The World Bank 2012 World Development Report on Gender Equality and Development (The World Bank 2011), which depicts the ways formal and informal institutions, markets and household factors combine and interact to determine gender-related outcomes. Policies need to consider those factors and their interactions to deliver on their intended outcomes and positively impact gender equality, which in turns, positively impacts economic growth and social development.

PAHO's framework is specifically adapted for gender analysis in the context of universal health coverage and explicitly emphasizes the causality between the multiple factors that drive change in gender equity in health across governance (which includes policies, legal and political structures at all state levels), health system performance and determinants of health (which acknowledges intersectionality) and ultimately social conditions (which includes gender roles, beliefs, social norms and communities). Those are represented by cogs, with movement and change in any cog, fuelled by policies or interventions, influencing other cogs, with change in social conditions impacting gender equality. Progress in gender equality can be measured in health status, but also in improved economic and social opportunities and political participation, which in turn drive sustainable development and growth. The framework also importantly reflects how barriers and constraints in any cog can hinder or even reverse change intended by policies and programmes.

Figure 2. PAHO's model for gender equality framework and indicators in the context of universal health and the Sustainable Development Goals (Pan American Health Organization 2019).

For the present thesis, this model was applied with a health financing lens, assessing only policies and interventions that address at least one of the three functions of a health financing system: revenue raising, fund pooling and purchasing (World Health Organization 2000). The framework is particularly relevant for the purpose of this review, as it considers the multiple, intertwined variables and factors that determined what it was about a policy or programme that works, for whom, under what circumstances and how, in addressing gender inequities and improving equality, rather than evaluating whether it worked.

Data extracted consequently included:

- Author, date, title, country
- Type of health financing policy or intervention
- Short description of outcomes and results on gender equity and equality
- Contribution to the tested theories (CMO), applying the framework for analysis
- Any additional factors highlighted in the documents that could support the development of new theories.

5. Evidence synthesis

Presented in the “Results” section, the findings were interpreted to confirm, contradict or refine the tested theories and formulate new ones. Because realist reviews do not aim to determine “best” practice, but to establish causal relationships between interventions and their contexts, it is not expected that findings result in the development of general recommendations (Pawson et al. 2005; Rycroft-Malone et al. 2012). In the “Discussion” section, conclusions are formulated with the aim to inform practitioners, especially at country level, on the contextual factors that are likely to influence the development and impact of gender-equitable health financing strategies.

Results

It was expected from the preliminary literature review that most of the literature that looks at gender and health financing and UHC focuses on studying countries, policies and programmes' gender equity challenges, with some explanatory research on the root causes for those inequities that helped formulate certain recommendations. Limited research focuses on studying policies and programmes that worked, even to some extent, and almost no literature looks to provide insights into the contextual factors that helped. The objective of the initial search strategy was therefore to identify the range of policies and programmes and country case studies for which there is evidence of some positive impact on gender inequities or inequalities in health financing. Based on the result of this search, specific groups of policies, programmes and countries could be defined and further researched to test the theories.

From the 22 documents selected during the initial search (see table 2), 13 articles focus on SRH, especially maternal health; 3 additional articles look at SRH, but not exclusively. 9 of those articles focus on DSF only, especially CCT, and only 2 are not discussing DSF. DSF and SRH represent therefore a focus area for this review. Of the 9 articles not focused on SRH or not only, 2 look at multiple financing mechanisms (the two articles used to formulate the initial CMO statements, that is Ravindran 2012 and Witter et al. 2017); 6 discuss at UHC schemes, which are therefore another focus area. Other health financing policies and programmes addressed include community-based health insurance (CBHI) and private micro-insurance schemes.

From a geographical perspective, 5 articles focus on India, 2 articles include India as part of the countries assessed and 6 more articles refer to policies and programmes in India; they discuss SRH-focused programmes such as CCTs as well as publicly-funded insurance schemes. 1 article focus on Mexico and 5 more articles look at Mexico among the countries studied, both for SRH-focused programmes such as CCTs and the UHC reform. 3 discuss Thailand's UHC reform and 2 articles focus on Indonesia's UHC reforms. Those countries are consequently of particular focus for this review.

The initial CMO statements, which are not mutually exclusive, are tested across those different programme-based and geographical focus areas, upon which the result section is therefore organised. As outlined in the search strategy, additional research was then performed to find further evidence on their contextual factors, with some articles from the preliminary search and some articles set aside during the initial search retrieved.

UHC reforms and publicly-funded schemes

Evidence gathered by Ravindran and Witter et al.'s papers highlighted the importance of proactive and explicit consideration of gender perspectives in the design of any health financing policies and programmes aiming to expand universal access (CMO 1). This implies that intentional decision-making is essential and that gender-neutral policies and programmes are in fact gender-blind and likely to perpetuate or even exacerbate existing gender inequities. Consideration of the multiple factors making women more vulnerable to catastrophic health expenditure and less likely to benefit from financial protection schemes entails that changes across other health systems blocks are likely to be necessary.

Both papers argue that in the same way, not all UHC reforms – which thrive for equitable access, are gender-equitable and that the intersection of gender with other determinants is largely underestimated, meaning large groups of women are less likely to enrol, utilise and benefit from UHC unless an intentional gender-perspective is applied when defining enrolment criteria, revenue collection and benefit packages (CMO 2). Those theories are essentially confirmed by the review, though with several nuances, leading to additional theories which are formulated after the assessment of several schemes and countries' reforms.

Thailand

In 2001 and within one year, Thailand implemented the Universal Coverage Scheme (UCS), combining three former schemes which had previously left 30% of the population uninsured, and operating in parallel with two other schemes still in place today: the Social Health Insurance Scheme, financed by payroll

contributions, which covers private sector employees and the Civil Servant Medical Benefit Scheme, financed by general tax revenue, which covers government employees and dependents. The UCS is financed by general tax revenue and covers 76% of the population. Entire households are covered. The deliberate intention to cover everyone without criteria and moving away from fragmentation is considered a key success factor, and was driven by a strong social movement that put UHC at the centre of political debates and elections. By 2015, only 0.1% of the population was still uninsured (Sen et al. 2018).

Evidence shows that the reform has rapidly improved the population's financial protection and utilisation, especially the most vulnerable: the share of OOP as a percentage of total health expenditure went from 34.1% in 2000 to 9% in 2021, with only 2.1% population incurring catastrophic OOP spending in 2021, one of the world's lowest incidence (World Bank 2024a; World Health Organization and World Bank 2023). The UCS's strong pro-poor and pro-rural focus has significantly improved income and geographic equity, having had the greatest impact on increased financial protection, healthcare utilization and poverty reduction among the poorest and rural populations (Limwattananon 2008).

The UCS's wide and explicit benefit package covers almost all SRH services recommended by the International Conference on Population and Development (ICPD). The country performs very strongly on SRH coverage indicators and evidence shows the equitable distribution of SRH services coverage between social groups and regions – rural areas even perform better in several maternal health indicators (World Health Organization 2024a). Limwattananon et al. 2010 found that more than socio-economic status, education was now the most important determinant of health inequity when looking at SRH indicators: for example, prevalence of adolescent pregnancy decreased sharply as the mother's formal education level increased. In fact, adolescent pregnancy, together with unsafe abortions and gender-based violence continue to represent major public health challenges (Sen et al. 2018).

In the identified studies, several factors are said to have contributed to Thailand's highly equitable UHC reform and are relevant for the present review. World Bank

2007, Limwattananon 2008 and Sen et al. 2018 highlight that the government had started to adopt pro-rural, pro-poor policies long before the 2001 UHC reform, by investing heavily in the health system infrastructure, particularly in the development of health facilities and trained workforce in rural areas. A 1971 policy installed a three-year mandatory rural service employment for all medical graduates. This means that when the UCS was implemented, the country already had the capacity to deliver a broad range of quality health services across all regions and populations. While the large, sudden increase in demand following the rapid implementation of UCS resulted in the healthcare providers challenging the increased workload and under-financing as well as in ongoing concerns on the scheme sustainability, the quality of services provided has been relatively sustained, with the vast majority of the population has been satisfied with health providers, availability of drugs and equipment (Ravindran 2011). The government adopted other supply side interventions to improve efficiency, such as, on the purchasing side, capitation and diagnosis-related groups (DRGs), which have been found to respond adequately to demand and utilisation (Tangcharoensathien V. et al. 2011).

World Bank 2007; Sen et al. 2018 also discuss the quality of the governance system set in place during and after the reform, relying on a sound balance between knowledge generation – a reliable information system – to continuously inform policy-making, strong political commitment and a pivotal role for civil society, supported by strong social movement and closely involved in the design, at the time, and management, today still, of the UCS. The cooperation between government and civil society, supported with evidence, has led to the continuous development of policies aiming to address large public health issues. For example, to tackle the rise of adolescent pregnancies, the Thai government engaged both the health and education sectors. The Ministry of Public Health revised the national reproductive health plan, focusing on youth-friendly health services and adolescent health, while the Ministry of Education implemented a sex education program in schools, though challenges with material quality and instructor training persisted. Thailand has also implemented early on gender-responsive training and resources for medical graduates and healthcare

workforce. The country's strong commitment to health have supported ongoing advances despite changing political landscapes.

Despite a high performance with gender and health indicators, there is evidence that inequities persist and that women are more affected by other social determinants of health compared to men (Chandoevmit and Phatchana 2019; World Health Organization 2024a). However, as mentioned by Sen et al. 2018, there is a lack of gender analyses of the Thai's UHC system, with limited literature applying a gender lens on the health policies, system's governance, health financing mechanisms, access to care and medicines beyond maternal health and SRH. Equity is essentially assessed in the context of income and geographies, and while gender is recognised as a determinant, it has not been proactively and specifically addressed in the context of financing policies.

Results from these findings seem to indicate that when health financing policies and schemes can effectively reduce intersectional inequities across geographies and income, provide a comprehensive, explicit benefit package and are backed by a strong healthcare delivery system that provides adequate primary care and referrals, women's financial barriers as well as some non-financial barriers to care can be addressed, even if they are not proactively and intentionally targeted.

Mexico

In 2003, the Social Protection System in Health (SPSS) was established, including the Seguro Popular (popular health insurance) scheme, with the aim to dramatically improve the poor and vulnerable population's financial protection. Seguro Popular was financed by general tax revenues and targeted everyone who was not covered by the existing social security schemes that covers formal sector employees and civil servants and mainly funded by payroll contributions. Similar to Thailand's UCS scheme, Seguro Popular had a large and explicit benefit package and is complemented by a special fund that covers catastrophic illness and complex disorders such as cancers, cardiovascular diseases or transplants (Sen et al. 2018). By 2016, 56 million people (43.5% of the total population) were enrolled in Seguro Popular and 10% of the total population was left uninsured (Knaul et al. 2023).

SPSS has been recognised for adopting a gender and life-course perspective with intentional efforts to improve women's health, including treatments critical for women across their lifetime and not just for the maternal and SRH needs - which are comprehensively covered by Seguro Popular - such as breast and cervical cancer treatments and mental health (Ibáñez X.A. 2015). Cultural barriers to women's access to care, for example in the case of cancer, have also been addressed in parallel with gender-sensitive awareness programmes to tackle stigma, discrimination and prejudices (Frenk et al. 2012). SPSS and Seguro Popular have rapidly been associated with uptake of maternal health and cancer prevention services and reduction of catastrophic OOP expenditures (Quick et al. 2014). OOP as a percentage of total health expenditure have however remained rather high, from 55.6% in 2003 to 41.4% in 2023, reaching their lower point in 2013 at 39.9% (World Bank 2024b). A National Center for Gender Equity and Reproductive Health was also created in 2003 to suggest and evaluate SRH-related policies and has since then been instrumental in the adoption of gender-sensitive budgets and monitoring of the health system performance and sex-disaggregated data collection (Frenk et al. 2012).

Mexico's UHC reform provides an interesting intersectional perspective. With over 90% of its members among the lower wealth quintiles, Seguro Popular has successfully focused on reaching the poorest families, among which a majority are female-headed households, which are generally overrepresented among informal workers and vulnerable populations (Knaul F.M. 2005). In addition, over 19% of Mexico's population self-identify as indigenous - one of the world's largest indigenous populations. Indigenous women are recognised to be among the most vulnerable groups in Mexico, being disproportionately affected by social and economic exclusion, gender-based violence and inequities, as discussed by Serván-Mori et al. 2021. This study shows that Seguro Popular was able to successfully reach indigenous populations, reaching 88% of indigenous women by 2019, a higher percentage than nonindigenous women, and reduce inequities in access and utilisation of care between indigenous and nonindigenous women. Contextual factors that contributed to this success include a clear prioritisation by the government of reaching those communities using tailored communication

efforts, leveraging engagement with community leaders and existing social networks set up by other government programmes that targeted indigenous communities.

Similarly to Thailand, evidence shows that a close collaboration between the government, which recognized the political opportunity associated with adopting such reforms and measures demanded by social movements, with women's health groups across civil society, NGOs, researchers and the media was instrumental in the implementation of policies (Frenk et al. 2012; Sen et al. 2018). However, enrolment numbers and efficiency of Seguro Popular against financial protection decreased from 2014 onwards, driven by reduced investment in health, resulting in deteriorating supply of services despite increasing demand and improved inefficiencies and misuse and increased reliance on private sector for healthcare delivery (Knaul et al. 2023). The new government formed in 2018 abolished Seguro Popular at the end of 2019 and created the Health Institute for Welfare (INSABI), which is substantially less funded and covers significantly less people than Seguro Popular used to (Knaul et al. 2023). These findings indicate that health financing reforms, despite supporting evidence and in the absence of strong and sustained social and public commitment, are vulnerable to political pressures and volatility.

Indonesia

Indonesia introduced its universal health insurance scheme in 2014, the National Social Security System (Jaminan Kesehatan Nasional, JKN). JKN integrates previous health schemes into one single pooled fund and is mandatory for all residents. The formal sector contributes through a 5% payroll contribution which cover their entire household; self-employed and informal sector workers pay set monthly premiums while the poor and disadvantaged groups do not pay any costs for the services covered. A separate entity from the Ministry of Health, the Social Security Management Agency (Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial or BPJS) was created to administrate JKN. As of August 2024, over 98% of the population is said to be covered by JKN (Jakarta Globe 2024). JKN has increased level of health insurance coverage among women in Indonesia and reduced their

financial barriers, resulting in increased utilisation for services like maternal health, though socio-economic inequalities remain (Rahmawati et al. 2024; Rahmawati and Hsieh 2024). There is no longer a difference in memberships between male-headed and female-headed households at the lowest poverty levels and wealthier women-headed households are even more likely to be members than male-headed ones (Sciortino 2023).

Civil society has played a pivotal and direct role in reducing those gender inequities in JKN's membership and utilisation and contributed to establish a gender-transformative UHC agenda. At the time of JKN launch, a range of women's groups and NGOs, jointly supported by the Indonesia and Australian governments strongly advocated for a gender-aware JKN, actively mobilised public authorities, activists and experts to identify and initiate activities to address gender inequities in benefit entitlement and benefit packages. Those groups collected evidence and led interventions towards four areas: 1) support eligible women get the documentation they needed to enrol, 2) advocate for changes in enrolment criteria that discriminated female-headed households, 3) develop a public monitoring and complain system to raise awareness on inequitable barriers and 4) communicate about JKN enrolment and benefits to women in areas hard to reach (Sciortino 2023).

Civil society also contributed to generating strong evidence of gaps and limitations of SRH service coverage and access, increase awareness and dialogues among communities on SRH and women's barriers to care and to advocate for policy changes. While the article concludes that the current policy and social environment remains challenging, even hostile to some changes, it confirms the critical role by civil society organisations can play as a bridge between government and communities and as drivers of change and accountability.

India

There is a large body of literature on India's inequalities and inequities, across social determinants of health (Ravindran and Gaitonde 2018). During the preliminary review and the initial search, a substantial number of results were

found to relate to India. While gender inequalities and inequities in access to financial protection and healthcare are well-researched, it is significantly more difficult to find evidence on health financing interventions that could address them. Many papers discuss those interventions' persisting gender disparities, very few discuss what has worked and why. However, some studies were identified that provide relevant information and context on how publicly-funded insurance schemes have started to reduce gender inequities (Cerceanu 2012; Sharma et al. 2023; Ziegler et al. 2024). Other schemes, such as gender-specific financing interventions like CCT are discussed later in the review.

India ranks among the world's worst countries in terms of gender equity (Raj 2011). Deeply-rooted historical, social and cultural norms have perpetuated pervasive and substantial discriminations against women across all aspects of society, which strongly intersect with significant and structural inequities based on geography, religion, caste and indigeneity (Ravindran and Gaitonde 2018).

Social health protection has historically been fragmented, characterised by dominant reliance on OOP (69.03% of total health expenditure in 2013, down to 49.82% in 2021 (World Bank 2024c)), a government-funded Central Government health scheme for central government employees, a limited payroll-based Employees' State Insurance Scheme (ESIS) for selected formal workers below a certain income level and multiple publicly-funded health insurance schemes (PFHIS) established at state levels, or in the case of former Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana (RSBY) and now Ayushman Bharat - Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PMJAY), at central government level, that essentially target Below the Poverty Line (BPL) populations. Those PFHIS were created to protect the most vulnerable against high OOP incurring from public and private hospital costs; consequently, they have historically not covered primary healthcare and have left a large part of the population, the one between the deprived and the formal and affluent populations, uncovered (Dubey et al. 2023).

For the purpose of this review, India brings relevant insights in two aspects: First, by looking at factors behind changes in women's enrolment and utilisation of the central government's PFHIS schemes, RSBY then PMJAY, and second by

looking at the large differences observed in gender equity indicators between different Indian states and their contextual factors.

Two studies analyse RSBY from a gender perspective (Cerceanu 2012; Ziegler et al. 2024), and other articles provide additional information on gender and PFHIS, especially as RSBY has now been replaced by PMJAY (RamPrakash and Lingam 2021; RamPrakash and Lakshmi 2018; Dubey et al. 2023). RSBY was launched in 2008 with the intention to provide cashless hospitalisation coverage to BPL population across India. RSBY was co-funded by the central and state governments and provided by insurance companies that are responsible for enrolment, which was voluntary, and claims management with contracted providers. The spouse was mandatorily enrolled with the household head and up to five family members could also enrol. Members were given a smartcard which provides cashless access to care – this mechanism has been largely praised – and was assumed to remove women’s needs to negotiate household resources. Overall, RSBY enrolment criteria and benefit packages were designed in a “gender-neutral” way, with the assumption that the needs are similar and similarly addressed for both genders. PMJAY has taken a similar stance.

In practice, the studies find that capping enrolment to five household members had a negative effect on the enrolment of daughters compared to son when the family counted more than five members. Many women still needed authorisation or presence of their husband to seek care or to pay for extra costs (both services and supplies not covered, but also undue payments required from providers) and faced discrimination and abuse from the health workers. While the scheme specifically targeted the poorest and most vulnerable segments of the population, many women, especially the illiterate, the elderly or the marginalised, were not or insufficiently informed of the existence and benefits of the scheme because the awareness campaigns, which were the responsibility of the insurers, was not adapted to them. Local communities, networks and NGOs could only play a limited role and RSBY ran in parallel to and with no integration with other PFHIS, leading to inefficiencies.

RSBY achieved good enrolment rates, though less than 60% of eligible families were enrolled by 2016. RSBY led to an increase in health service utilisation, but its insufficient annual cap was associated to a 30% increased likelihood of incurring OOP as well as an increase health expenditure-induced poverty (Dubey et al. 2023). PMJAY was therefore introduced in 2018 by the new government, with the intention to scale but improve RSBY towards a larger UHC ambition. Similar in design and structure, PMJAY however has a larger cap and benefit package, though still not including most outpatient care. Eligibility and enrolment criteria are broader; there is no longer a limit on the number of household members, which is a direct learning from RSBY's gender bias (Ziegler et al. 2024). States can also continue to run their PFHIS in collaboration with PMJAY. Accountability for awareness and enrolment is shared by the local governments and the insurers (Dubey et al. 2023).

The studies find that overall and, in most states, enrolment under both schemes has been relatively equal for men and women. In addition, women as well as female-headed households have been more likely to enrol in the schemes than men. In the case of RSBY, older women were however less likely to enrol, as well daughters and other female household members beyond the spouse, which was mandatorily involved, meaning that those results are directly related to enrolment criteria and conditions. The obligatory presence of the household head for the enrolment process, while male household heads are more likely to be employed and away than female heads may in part explain the higher chance of enrolment by female-headed households; evidence has also showed that women, when they have the decision-making power for it, tend to invest more in their family's health and welfare (Finnoff 2016).

Large difference in utilisation have however been observed. Overall, under PMJAY, the volume and per-capita value of claims is significantly higher for men and most of the portability (opportunity to seek care outside of the state of residence, a feature used to access specialised care) and readmission rates are male. More male claims are seen at private hospitals and for tertiary conditions, while more female claims are seen at public hospitals and for secondary

conditions. Most procedures covered, ranging from general to specialised medicine and surgery or cardiology are more utilised by men; higher utilisation by women was essentially found in OBGYN, ophthalmology and medical oncology (Dubey et al. 2023).

Variation in gender differences for enrolment and utilisation was found between states, which is interesting to further examine for the purpose of our theory testing. Despite not being the most economically developed, India's Southern states like Kerala, Tamil Nadu or Andhra Pradesh have historically had far better social development indicators such as health, education, literacy and income than most other Indian states or the national average. Gender equality indicators, such as literacy and education levels, female life expectancy and sex ratio have also been historically much higher, especially in Kerala and Southern women benefit from much higher empowerment levels than their counterparts in other states; they are more likely to marry later and a husband they chose, have more control over resources, work and move more freely, regardless of their wealth, caste and religion (Jejeebhoy and Sathar 2001; Devi 2012; Evans 2020). Women's empowerment in Kerala is also recognised as having directly contributed to the state's strong social development (Devi 2012). Strong investments in primary healthcare network and healthcare infrastructure have contributed to high performance in key indicators such as access to ANC and maternal mortality (Baru et al. 2010). Some southern states record higher population enrolment in their state insurance schemes than the rest of the country, with up to 80% of the population covered (Sharma et al. 2023).

Multiple historical and political factors can explain this difference, including the historical absence of purdah and labour-intensive agriculture in Southern states, state governments' prioritisation of welfare-oriented policies and the role of a socially engaged population (Devi 2012; Evans 2020), which are relevant factors for this review. Northeastern states like Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya or Sikkim have also shown slightly better-than-national-average gender indicators, one explanation for which is the prevalence of tribal and indigenous culture, where women and men are considered equal (Borah 2019). Those Southern and

Northeastern states' performance should however be assessed keeping in mind that the country has one of the world's lowest women empowerment levels (Jejeebhoy and Sathar 2001) and that those achievements are not secured and have in fact tended to degrade in recent years (Evans 2020).

In the context of gender and health financing, a study shows that PFHIS coverage in southern states is increasingly in favour of the poorer and less educated population, however large inequalities persist or are even worsening for women across caste, religion and education (Sharma et al. 2023). This confirms that "gender-neutral" schemes fail at improving women's vulnerability to other social determinants of health. As already emphasized by Ravindran 2012, the study shows that non-BPL women, especially from middle-income segments face increasing financial barriers, as they are less likely to be covered by public insurance schemes and face prohibitive OOP.

While several Southern and Northeastern states have higher enrolment for women than men, claim volume and value are higher for men, meaning insurance coverage does not necessarily translate in higher utilisation (Dubey et al. 2023). Only two northeastern states, Sikkim and Meghalaya, recorded higher claims for women than men after excluding obstetrics and gynaecology. Another study in Southern state Andhra Pradesh confirms that at equal coverage with men and for free services, for sex-neutral conditions, women accessed a smaller proportion of care than men (Shaikh M et al. 2018). These are interesting findings as from a theory testing perspective, states with better supply-side infrastructure and higher women empowerment would be expected to perform better.

Another study shows that women incur larger OOP compared to men despite PFHIS coverage, because they are charged undue fees, medicine and transportation costs and face discrimination for pre-authorisation or hospital admittance. Most importantly, many of their basic needs such as SRH are not covered, including in Southern states' schemes (RamPrakash and Lakshmi 2018; Philip and Ravindran 2017; RamPrakash and Lingam 2021).

One study found that female local political representation reduces the gender gap by increasing the focus on women's health needs and barriers and contributing

to improving women's empowerment and so their awareness and use of insurance schemes (Dupas and Jain 2021). As female representation remains very low and as male preference is prevalent across India, even in states where women are more empowered, this implies that policies aiming to tackle local social and cultural norms are critical even when the infrastructure appears more favourable.

Other insurance schemes

Private health insurance

Witter et al. 2017 discusses that private voluntary insurance is inequitable because it generally excludes the unemployed and socio-economically vulnerable, among which women are overrepresented and are less likely to provide adequate coverage in areas where women have higher needs, including SRH. Because of lower employment rates and lower salaries, women are less likely to have access to employer-sponsored insurance and to afford insurance overall. In addition, on the basis that women account for a higher average use of health services compared to men, gender-based pricing is frequently applied across private health insurance markets worldwide, meaning women's premiums are usually higher than that of men. This strongly reinforces gender inequities in access to private insurance coverage.

The paper mentions that explicit policy measures can be taken to reduce those inequities, such as in the USA. A study (Lee et al. 2020) shows that the Affordable Care Act (ACA), implemented in the USA in 2010, took a gender-transformative approach to private insurance coverage with the introduction of premium subsidies for low-income or unemployed women; the obligation for insurers to cover essential health benefits, including maternal health or mental health, to cover without cost-sharing a range of preventive services relevant for women across their lifecycle; the interdiction to apply an annual cap on those essential benefits, to deny coverage based on preexisting conditions such as pregnancy, infertility, history of intimate partner violence, and sexual assault and to apply a premium rating based on gender and pre-existing conditions. That study mentioned that prior to ACA, women's premium could cost up to 84% more than

men's, totalling an estimated USD 1 billion more per year. The study provides evidence that after the introduction of ACA, women were more likely to be insured, to be able to afford health insurance and care, and to receive preventive care. It resulted in an increased use of contraception, ANC and led to improved maternal health outcomes.

Another study that assessed the impact of the 2011 European Union's ban of gender-pricing, which was adopted specifically in the name of gender equity, on private insurance coverage in Germany confirms that this increased the likelihood of women to enrol to a private insurance schemes, with no evidence that this negatively impacted adverse risk selection (Huang and Salm 2020). In South Africa, medical schemes are not permitted to apply gender-rating either (Govender et al. 2014).

While the studies also emphasize that gender and intersectional inequities based on income, race or ethnicity largely persist among women in the US and South Africa, those findings confirm that policies applying a gender perspective in enrolment criteria, premium subsidies and benefit packages positively improve women's access to financial protection schemes, their use of healthcare services and health outcomes. Without those conscious efforts, women are often discriminated against by health financing systems compared to men.

In both the US and South Africa, private health insurers play a key financial protection role in the health system, which explains why policies to regulate the market can translate into measurable impact at population level. The political context plays a critical role for those reforms, with the government taking a strong position towards improving inequities in healthcare, using healthcare reforms to advance a political agenda, as was seen in Mexico or Thailand for example. In the US like for Mexico, political volatility is however also a challenge in reform stability, as advances by the ACA such as access to SRH is now jeopardised.

Community-based health insurance (CBHI) schemes

One paper discusses whether CBHI can contribute to achieve equitable financial protection and UHC using the example of Burkina Faso (Parmar et al. 2014). It

defines CBHI schemes as “voluntary, non-profit insurance schemes, formed on the basis of an ethic of mutual aid, solidarity and collective pooling of health risks, in which the members participate effectively in its management and functioning”. It argues that while CBHI schemes have major constraints in that their risk-pooling capacity is by nature limited and the services they can cover consequently restricted, they can represent, if integrated, an opportunity for countries whose progress towards UHC is hindered by a severely inadequate fiscal space and high informal employment rates. Integration of CBHI into a UHC strategy is for example the path taken in Rwanda, which is also discussed.

Parmar et al. 2014 finds that there is no significant association of gender to enrolment, but that women are disproportionately affected by other factors negatively impacting enrolment and utilisation, such as wealth, residence, education and employment. While utilization was not significantly different between enrolled men and women, women enrolled were found to have higher utilization of care services compared to women without CBHI – a difference that was not observed between enrolled and non-enrolled men. This implies that CBHI can reduce gender inequities in utilisation of healthcare. However, the study finds that CBHI was ineffective at removing critical non-financial barriers such as distance.

All those findings are not unique to Burkina Faso and align with consistent evidence from many other CBHI schemes in Africa including Ghana’s National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS), a national voluntary health insurance programme also established to consolidate prior CBHI schemes, as well as other voluntary health insurance schemes in Africa or the previously discussed PFHIS in India (Chirwa et al. 2021; Sen et al. 2018; Shao et al. 2022; Kawuki et al. 2022). It confirms the hypothesis that health financing policies and programmes, should adopt gender-sensitive and intersectional approaches to effectively expand and sustain their impact.

Several studies assessing gender equity in the context of Rwanda’s CBHI-based social health insurance system provide relevant information for further theory testing (Sen et al. 2018; Chirwa et al. 2021; Finnoff 2016; Kawuki et al. 2022;

Chemouni 2018). What started as a few segmented CBHI schemes in 1999 was rolled out across the country by the government in 2005 and followed, with an ambition towards UHC, by a series of reforms that made enrolment mandatory - covering more than 90% of the population today, making it the most successful national insurance scheme in Sub-Saharan Africa. Benefit packages were standardised, an income-based contribution category system was established, according to which members pay a different premium based on their income, while the government subsidises premiums for the poorest and most vulnerable populations (Sen et al. 2018). The system appears effective in reaching most vulnerable women and consider intersectional barriers as the studies found that female-headed households have lower CBHI expenditure than men, meaning they benefit most often from the government subsidies, and women with lower decision-making power and lower economic empowerment were more likely to utilise their insurance coverage than their counterparts.

Evidence from the studies shows the influence of Rwanda's particular political context. Rwanda ranks among the best countries in women empowerment with women scoring higher than men in some indicators such as literacy, education or seats held in the national parliament (the world's highest proportion) and in government offices (Kawuki et al. 2022). Following the 1994 genocide, women made up most of the surviving population, became heads of households and their role in society evolved, with the government recognizing the importance of women empowerment to rebuild the country and incorporating its commitment to gender equity in the constitution and legal framework. As a result, despite persisting gendered social and cultural norms, Rwanda has achieved high gender equality, which is reflected in the adoption of gender-responsive policies, as well as the creation of bodies and agencies at national and local government and community levels to support gender equity and women's empowerment (USAID 2014).

Furthermore, another study discusses the importance of analysing Rwanda's unique CBHI scheme from a political context perspective (Chemouni 2018). Rwanda has been ruled by the same party, the RPF – which is also the country's

unique party, since 1994 and the same president, Paul Kagame, since 2000. This has given the government a long-term horizon and the ability to develop an institutionalised, universal protection scheme, including through the adoption of unpopular measures at the time, such as mandatory enrolment - largely recognised as a necessary condition to achieve universality (Kutzin J. 2012), or income-based premium contributions. It also allowed the building of a large healthcare delivery network with a decentralised, but vertically integrated governance system. In addition, the CBHI scheme and broader health system strengthening has also been durably and heavily subsidised by donors, which was enabled by Rwanda's post-genocide reconstruction context and provided the government with the means to implement its reform over time while sustaining a pro-poor subsidised system.

Microinsurance programmes

One paper looks at what are the factors to consider to develop gender-sensitive microinsurance programmes (Banthia et al. 2009), recognising that women are particularly vulnerable – and therefore should be especially targeted by such programmes - and respond differently to different risks than men, implying that an intersectional approach is needed to effectively reach them. It defines microinsurance as “protection of low-income people against specific perils in exchange for regular premium payments proportionate to the likelihood and cost of the risk involved”. In the context of the study, microinsurance programmes differs from CBHI in that they are not community-driven, rather co-developed by financial institutions that usually operate on a for-profit basis. It argues that programmes that best reach vulnerable women include women-specific risks, are designed and distributed in a way that consider them as household risk and resource managers and as the primary caregiver, while actively considering gender dynamics and power relations in the households.

This entails covering women's health needs through their lifecycle, including maternal health and SRH services, often excluded from micro health insurance programmes or insufficiently covered, but also the needs of their entire family. Some viable programmes have also offered the opportunity for women to pick

and choose from a list of benefits, empowering them to choose based on their households' needs. Programmes that recognise that women, in many contexts, are more risk-adverse than men and need more information before making a purchasing decision, which can also be driven by intra-household power relations, have proven more successful. Risk-adversity is also means that women, provided they can afford it, are more likely to value the opportunity to provide financial protection for their family, which applies to other forms of voluntary insurance schemes like CBHI (Finnoff 2016). Successful programmes also use simple and easy terms to adapt to low education and literacy levels, women-only forums, women sales force from the local communities and regular face to face interactions throughout the duration of the enrolment to also address utilisation. This also aligns with the findings from the national schemes discussed previously.

In conclusion, the analysis of several countries' reforms and health financing policies and programmes generally confirm CMO statements 1 and 2. The findings, assessed using the conceptual framework described in the Methods section, provide additional information and nuances to further elaborate the initial theories, and new CMOs can be formulated.

While women are less likely to enrol in payroll-based insurance schemes, it was found that enrolment is more equitable in tax-revenue-funded schemes, whether they are insurance-based like in India or Rwanda or universal schemes, like in Thailand or Mexico. When not universal, targeted communication efforts help reach women, especially vulnerable women. However, utilisation was found to be persistently inequitable, in varying levels, based on several factors, such as inadequate benefit packages, gendered supply-side access barriers to quality care or persisting social and cultural norms preventing women from seeking care. Contextual factors such as a good healthcare delivery infrastructure network, enduring political commitment and effective social participation influence the success of a health policy or programme at addressing gender inequities. This leads to the formulation of the following CMO statements:

Complementing CMO 1 configuration:

- For voluntary health insurance schemes (C), reforms and programmes that apply gender-neutral pricing or provide subsidies or income-based premium rating and include all family members (M) will meaningfully tackle gendered socio-economic disparities and improve women's enrolment in the scheme (O).
- For voluntary health insurance schemes (C), providing an explicit benefit package that specifically address women's basic health needs across their lifecycles, including preventive services (M) will enhance women's uptake and sustainable, viable use of the scheme (O).
- Health financing policies and programmes' awareness and promotion campaigns (C) that leverage local community networks, women's groups and women leaders, community health workers (M) are more likely to effectively address social and cultural barriers, reach women and female-headed households from various socio-economic backgrounds and ensure they can benefit from the scheme (O).

Complementing CMO 2 configuration:

- As they design and implement UHC reforms (C), governments that effectively support social participation and actively collaborate with civil society, women's groups, NGOs and community networks (M) ensure that they are responsive to gendered and intersectional needs and significantly enhances uptake and utilisation of UHC schemes.
- In contexts where rural and vulnerable communities benefit from a strong primary healthcare infrastructure network and referral system (C) UHC scheme that provide a comprehensive, explicit package that includes outpatient care (M) can address key gendered financial and non-financial barriers even if women are not specifically targeted (O).
- Publicly-funded schemes that claim to be gender-neutral (C) may achieve equal enrolment between men and women, but can only progress towards gender-equitable utilisation and reduced OOP spend (O) if they explicitly target women's special health needs, starting with SRH services (M).

Demand-side financing mechanisms and SRH services

Ravindran and Witter et al.'s papers found that gender-specific health financing policies and interventions should be combined with complementary measures to effectively address the barriers affecting women's ability to pay for and access healthcare, because affordability intersects with several other gendered structural and social determinants. Evidence for gender-specific financing interventions that specifically aim to address women's health needs is essentially focused on maternal health and SRH services. Those interventions include DSF mechanisms such as conditional cash transfers, vouchers or the removal or reduction of user fees for maternal health and SRH services.

This led to the CMO 3 configuration: Gender-specific interventions, such as removal of user fees and conditional cash-transfers for maternal and sexual and reproductive health services (C) that are combined with measures to tackle underlying cultural, political and social determinants that undermine women and girls' access to care (M) are more likely to reach their intended outcomes (O).

Public, private and community-based insurance schemes, social health insurance schemes or tax-based schemes, previously discussed, are not considered here gender-specific interventions because they do not provide financial protection for women's health needs only. From the initial search, 13 studies provided additional information to confirm and refine this theory. As outlined in the search strategy, more articles were then identified for additional context to test the initial theory.

All studies confirm that CCTs, vouchers and user fee removal policies help reduce income-related inequities and consistently increase women's use of maternal and SRH health services and reduce their OOP expenditure, but that a critical success factor is their combination with additional measures to maximise and sustain their impact. Those additional measures include supply-side approaches to address the quality and capacity of healthcare delivery as well as interventions that address women's non-financial demand-side barriers. Adequate design and governance are also important (Ahmed S. 2011; Balasubramanian P. 2012; Barber and Gertler 2009; De Allegri et al. 2011; Lim

et al. 2010; Parkhurst J.O. et al. 2005; Ravindran and Govender 2020; Witter S. et al. 2016; Witter and Ensor op. 2012; Witter and Somanathan 2012; Appleford et al. 2020; Hellwig and Barros 2022; Plouffe V. et al. 2020).

Supply-side approaches

DSF mechanisms predominantly aim to address financial barriers to care and are based on the recognition that supply-side financing is inequitable and not enough to address the specific needs of the vulnerable population, including women. However, several studies confirm that the DSF interventions that perform most strongly are complemented by supply-side interventions to improve the capacity and quality of healthcare delivery (Witter and Somanathan 2012; Witter and Ensor op. 2012; Ahmed S. 2011). Some of those measures do not address gender-related barriers specifically, but are relevant factors to consider. This implies, from a theory perspective, that combining gender-specific interventions with meaningful investments in the delivery system may be at least as important as addressing non-financial gender-related barriers to care.

Witter et al. 2017 reported evidence that higher utilisation following the introduction of DSF without proper infrastructure investment has often led to strained, poorly trained and equipped healthcare workers and consequently, harmful practices. One study capturing initial learnings from Bangladesh's Maternal Health Voucher Scheme (MHVS), introduced in 2007 and still in place today, found the scheme's impact to be negatively impacted by the facilities' limited capacity as well as the lack of specialised physicians in some areas (such as obstetrician-gynaecologists and anaesthesiologists). Such shortages led some women to be referred to other facilities and incur additional costs for travel (despite the scheme covering travel costs to a certain amount), food and accommodation for which they had to resort to coping strategies such as loans, defeating the scheme's purpose. Lim et al. 2010 argues that differential uptakes by districts of India's national CCT scheme Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) are influenced by variation in infrastructure and that increased workloads led to reduced quality of care, such as early discharge after deliver delivery. Another study confirms such findings to apply to several DSF schemes in India and other

countries (Hunter and Murray 2017). Distance, and specifically the costs associated to transportation, is consistently mentioned as one of women's most important barriers, in accessing healthcare (De Allegri et al. 2011; Hellwig and Barros 2022). To address pre-existing infrastructure limitations, Witter and Somanathan 2012 mentions that in Nepal, the roll-out of the Safe delivery Incentive Programme (SDIP), also introduced in 2007 and still in place today, was accompanied by considerable other investments in establishing and equipping birthing centres and improving training of staff, amongst other activities and that travel costs were also included. More recent evidence demonstrated that sustained supply-side investments, especially in the most remote areas enabled the SDIP to reach its intended outcomes, though large gaps remain (Ensor et al. 2017). Covering travel costs, similar supply side investments and capacity adjustments have also supported India JSY scheme, amongst other programmes (Hunter and Murray 2017; Parkhurst J.O. et al. 2005).

Ahmed S. 2011 found that utilisation of maternal health services only increased after the MHVS allowed healthcare providers to receive incentive payments for the provision of services to enrolled women. The study also mentions that incentive payments are most effective if there is market competition, which may attract private providers and increase capacity, but also provides incentives to deliver better quality services in both public and private sectors, especially if the scheme does not include an increase of the supply of healthcare providers, equipment and personnel. Scheme administrators should also be eligible for incentive payments. Two other papers confirm similar findings, with the implementation of supply-side measures such as provider incentives linked to uptake of services and performance-based contracting playing a critical role in the scheme's impact in Nepal's SDIP and other voucher programmes in Cambodia, Kenya or Uganda (Witter and Somanathan 2012; Hunter and Murray 2017).

Another study which assesses the impact of policies to remove and reduce fees for obstetric care in Benin, Burkina Faso, Mali and Morocco (Witter S. et al. 2016) brings nuance to the theory that the introduction of the health financing

intervention need to be accompanied by meaningful investments in the delivery system and adequate incentive structures, to absorb the expected and desired increase in utilisation. Those policies were thoroughly implemented and have achieved substantial reductions in OOP. The study highlights that out of the four countries, only Morocco accompanied the policy with investments in staffing and access to care. Increased workload was reported in Morocco, Benin and Burkina Faso, yet across all countries “the majority of staff surveyed felt positive about the wider effects of the policy, believing that the policy has increased access to skilled birth attendance, has benefited the poor, and has improved the quality of care, including through perceived improvements to drugs and supplies”. Women generally perceived the overall quality of the services to be high or very high, which does not correlate with technical quality, which was measured to be in fact rather poor, especially in Burkina Faso (where women were the most satisfied) and Benin. Morocco’s hospitals did perform consistently better, but the study cannot associate this to additional investments in staff and resources.

The study hypothesised that an increase in volume of patients, if not met with an increase in human resources, might lead to a deterioration of the quality of care, but could not find such association and concluded that quality of the care provided is affected by many factors which may not all relate to the policies, though in all four countries they paid too little attention to improving the quality of care. Neither of the four countries included incentive payments to providers. Fixed provider payment structures in Benin and Mali were found to be poorly calibrated and either over-incentivise or under-fund, resulting in perverse effects.

One supply-side performance factor which has direct gender implications, and which can also be influenced by adequate incentives and purchasing side strategies is the provider-patient interaction. Several studies discuss the well-evidenced disrespect, abuse and discriminatory attitudes experienced by women in health facilities, particularly in the context of maternal health and SRH and despite the introduction of gender-specific policies, which are disempowering and discourage them from seeking healthcare (Plouffe V. et al. 2020; Ravindran 2012; De Allegri et al. 2011; Appleford et al. 2020). Gender-based discriminations at

facilities also intersect with prejudices based on disability, ethnicity and religion, further influencing women's negative experience with healthcare providers and consequently their care-seeking behaviours (De Allegri et al. 2011). Overworked health workers may be more prone to such abuse (Ravindran 2012), which means that the introduction of DSF mechanisms without adequate supply-side interventions to mitigate the impact of increased demand on providers is likely to reinforce such practices. Introducing certain payment and purchasing strategies can impact providers' behaviours. Pay-for-performance (P4P), which provides bonus payments to providers to incentivise them for improvements in utilization and quality of care indicators can have a large, positive impact on the willingness by trained health workers to deliver not only better quality maternal health and SRH care, but also to encourage women to seek skilled healthcare, as demonstrated in Rwanda (Witter and Ensor op. 2012; Basinga et al. 2010).

Interventions to address non-financial barriers

As previously discussed, there is a vast amount of evidence that shows how social and cultural norms negatively affect women's ability to benefit from health financing programmes. SRH is an area where social and cultural factors tend to play an especially important role both at policy-making level and household health seeking behaviours and several studies discuss how addressing women's underlying, non-financial barriers to care increased the impact of maternal health and SRH financing policies.

Plouffe et al. 2020 argues that while DSF can improve women's agency to receive healthcare, primarily because it reduces their need to negotiate access to household resources, which has been established as a common barrier for women to access to healthcare in low-income countries, it does little on its own to address other critical barriers driven by lack of control over resources and persisting influence of social norms. They may still need the husband's permission before seeking care, even if it's free and depend on him for other related costs such as transportation, medication not covered or informal payments. Lack of access to two other critical form of resources, information and education, also restrict women's healthcare decision-making. It undermines

women's confidence to interact with healthcare providers and fosters their dependence on the decisions and opinions of others in their household or the community, which are driven by social norms and beliefs which can discourage them from seeking healthcare, even if it's free. Women's education level has been found to be consistently associated with higher utilisation of a financial protection scheme, even when it initially and specifically targets the most vulnerable women (Lim et al. 2010; Balasubramanian P. 2012; De Allegri et al. 2011; Hellwig and Barros 2022).

Witter and Somanathan 2012 finds that communication and marketing strategies tailored to the health financing intervention and the target population, considering social determinant such as education and literacy, their community and social and cultural environment are critical to their uptake. For example, in Uganda, a voucher scheme used a combination of community-based sensitisation, use of radio and incentives for distributors; in Kenya, a voucher scheme developed different marketing strategies to adapt to the different needs between urban and rural areas, a range of marketing strategies had to be developed; in Pakistan, the voucher scheme's communication strategy included several visits per household and testimony from trusted community members to address cultural barriers and misconceptions. Leveraging networks of women's groups, as seen with Mexico's Oportunidades or Nepal's SDIP also helps deliver tailored information to women (Hunter and Murray 2017).

Involving men, at community level for example, husbands and other members of household or family like the husband or parents-in-laws can help reduce social barriers hindering women's healthcare decision-making. In Rwanda, encouraging the participation of men and the whole community in family planning discussions was a key factor contributing to increase coverage significantly (Hellwig and Barros 2022). Another study confirms this finding in the context of Tanzania's national health insurance, where male involvement in ANC improved their awareness of the scheme and consequently their support in utilising it (Morgan et al. 2018).

The case of Mexico's Oportunidades, then called Prospera, is interesting. Established In 1997 (originally called Progresa), Prospera was a large-scale CCT that provided incentives for low-income families, in both rural and urban areas, to invest in their children's health and education so that they obtain the capabilities necessary to escape poverty when they reach adulthood. The programme's impact on poverty reduction, education and certain health outcomes, especially for children, has largely been documented. One of the largest CCT worldwide, it covered over 26 million people in Mexico (about 20% of the total population), including 50% of people in extreme poverty (70% in rural areas), 28% in moderate poverty and 11% non-poor households (Núñez 2023). Enrolled households receive conditional monthly benefits for at least three years.

While not primarily targeting women's health needs, Prospera took a gender-sensitive approach. Pregnant women were for example required to complete ANC and all adult beneficiaries to attend preventive medical check-ups and an educational programme about health prevention and care content. An important feature of the programme was the deliberate decision to give the cash transfers only to the mother or female head of the household. Women beneficiaries attended regular meetings with programme' elected representatives, a key objective of which was to encourage women to be proactive in obtaining their right to healthcare and social services (Barber and Gertler 2009). The evidence suggests that those features directly increased the quality of ANC received by beneficiaries by empowering women to expect better care through information and by giving them self-confidence in their interactions with healthcare providers (Barber and Gertler 2009). This is a relevant demand-side strategy to address abusive and discriminatory provider-patient relations which, as previously discussed, is a critical consideration for women's health-seeking behaviour. Another study finds that by making them the recipients of the CCT, Prospera increased women's bargaining position and status within their households, which reduced intra-household gender inequities in land owning and income sharing (Radel et al. 2017). Prospera was eliminated, like the Seguro Popular, by President Obrador when he took office in December 2018. It was replaced by two smaller programmes focusing children education and evidence found that its

elimination contributed to increased poverty and inequality during the COVID pandemic (Knaul et al. 2023). As discussed earlier, political volatility can negatively influence the needed governments' enduring commitment to relevant policies and programmes.

India's JSY also provides an interesting case of addressing women's community and social barriers to utilisation of maternal healthcare. JSY is implemented through the close to one million Accredited Social Health Activists (ASHAs), a type of community health workers deployed in almost all rural villages of India since 2005 who work as an interface between the community and the public health system (Lim et al. 2010). ASHAs are trained local women who create awareness on health, its social determinants and help the community access health services, especially women and children. In the context of JSY, they are responsible for identifying pregnant women and help them get to a health facility. ASHAs challenge communities' and family's reluctance in receiving skilled maternal care and provide practical support to mothers, for example finding means of transportation to a healthcare facility, helping them engage with providers, etc.

JSY is financed by central government and provides women cash incentives to deliver in a health facility, including limited coverage for transportation costs (found to be often insufficient). In ten "low performance" states (LPS) – those performing most poorly in terms of maternal mortality ratio – all pregnant women irrespective of socioeconomic status and parity delivering in a public facility or accredited private facility are eligible for the cash benefit; in all other states – the "high performance states" or HPS, women are only eligible for the cash benefit (lower than in LPS) for their first two livebirths, and if they are below-the-poverty-line (BPL) or from a scheduled (low) caste or tribe.

In LPS, ASHAs receive performance-linked cash incentive for each in-facility delivery they assisted. While awareness of JSY was found to be very low in the first years and varies across states (Lim et al. 2010; Witter and Somanathan 2012), awareness of and satisfaction with ASHA's support has been high among women and their communities (United Nations Population Fund 2009) and

evidence now shows that ASHAs are associated with improved ANC utilization, ANC quality, early initiation of breastfeeding and reduced infant mortality (Nadella et al. 2021) and that they have played a pivotal role in making institutional deliveries an increasing social norm across India and (Gupta et al. 2018). While ASHAs suffer from poor compensation, poor recognition, respect and support from public services and formal health sector players (Dasgupta et al. 2022), in the context of JSY, they have been pivotal in addressing Indian women's non-financial barriers to care. This is an important factor given persisting inequities discussed earlier in the context of PFHIS.

Adequate design and governance

Several studies discuss the importance of applying an intersectional gender lens when defining the policy or intervention's design and governance. Criteria and methods applied for enrolment are critical as they can exclude some of the women they initially meant to target or include more than initially targeted, putting the scheme's sustainability and effectiveness at risk (Ahmed S. 2011; Witter and Somanathan 2012; Balasubramanian P. 2012). For example, DSF that only covers the first two deliveries or require extensive formal identification exclude a large segment of women from the most vulnerable segments (among the poorest, the lower castes or minority populations or adolescents) where fertility is at the highest, who lack documentation or literacy. In priority Indian states (those with lower performance indicators), all pregnant women are eligible to receive JSY benefits (Lim et al. 2010). Having a very well defined target population – which evolves over time based on needs and capacity - with clear, transparent mechanisms for selecting the beneficiaries is considered one of the main success factors of Mexico's Prospera (World Bank 2016).

Confirming findings from national and UHC schemes, strong political commitment and central government's support and budget, as is the case for Mexico's Prospera, India's JSY, Nepal's SDIP or user fee removal in Morocco, are also found to be important success factors (Witter S. et al. 2016; Witter and Somanathan 2012). This does not mean that programmes should be centrally managed; in fact, policies that encourage local governments and providers'

accountability and commitment, have a strong local presence and network to ensure alignment and engagement with local needs and communities have been found to be factors facilitating a positive policy adaptation in many contexts and to address non-financial barriers for women (Witter S. et al. 2016; Witter and Somanathan 2012; Hellwig and Barros 2022; World Bank 2016).

Regardless of the local health system structure, countries which have best sustained gender-specific, DSF policies appear to have those policies well integrated with and an integral part of a broader political commitment and strategy towards UHC, more equitable financial protection and welfare, like in Nepal, Bangladesh or India (Hunter and Murray 2017; Ahmed S. 2011; Hellwig and Barros 2022; Witter and Somanathan 2012). This also aligns with findings confirming that such financing policies are more likely to be impactful if they are combined with delivery system strengthening interventions.

A solid monitoring and evaluation agenda will also lead to an improved policy and programme design over time, ensuring that shortcomings in reaching targeted women in intended ways are addressed, as was found in Mexico, India or Nepal for example (Hunter and Murray 2017; World Bank 2016).

In conclusion, the initial CMO 3 configuration can be further elaborated. The review for example found that supply-side interventions, not all directly aimed at tackling gender-related barriers can be at least as critical to sustain the impact of gender-specific, demand-side financing policies and programmes as interventions tackling non-financial, demand-side barriers. The following CMO configurations can therefore be formulated:

- The implementation of gender-specific DSF policies (C) should be combined with appropriate supply-side investments that strengthen infrastructure and address healthcare workers' additional workload (M) to ensure that the local healthcare delivery system has the capacity to meet the increased demand (O).
- Gender-specific DSF policies (C) that also implement adequate incentive structures for providers and healthcare workers which encourage both

higher quality care and respectful, non-discriminatory interactions (M) are more likely to address gendered barriers to care and effectively improve women's utilisation of services (O).

- When rolling out gender-specific financing programmes (C) including tailored information and communication strategies that equip women with the knowledge and self-confidence to make informed health decisions and increase their bargaining position within their households and communities (M) improves women's ability to use the programme and access health services (O).
- In local contexts where social and cultural barriers and power relations play an as equally important role as affordability in preventing women from accessing skilled maternal and sexual and reproductive healthcare (C), gender-specific financing policies should be combined with community engagement and education interventions (M) to reach their intended outcomes (O).
- Gender specific policies (C) that are continuously based on evidence and integrated into governments' commitment and coordinated efforts towards UHC and equitable access to healthcare (M) are more sustainable, inclusive and adaptive and therefore fit to address the diverse needs of the women they target (O).

Discussion

The purpose of this review was to define the conditions for the success of policies and programmes in addressing gender inequities in health financing that affect women's ability to access and utilise healthcare services, according to their needs without financial hardship, compared to men. After identifying health financing policies and programmes for which there is evidence of a positive impact on gender inequities, the review assessed what are the different factors that contributed to this impact. PAHO's framework for gender equality in the context of UHC helped assess how policies and programme can influence inequities across different categories of factors, that are considered as connected cogs: governance, health system performance and determinants of health, which together can drive changes in women's social conditions that affect how equal they are, compared to men, notably in access to healthcare and health status.

Political will and commitment emerged as one of the most important factors. Across the different contexts where UHC reforms or health financing policies, such as DSF, have led to meaningful progress towards equality, including gender equality, political leadership was considered critical to enable policy realisation, more so than evidence or the influence of international organisations. Political will is fuelled for different reasons – it can be a new government that has committed to drive change requested by social movements, as discussed in Thailand, Mexico, the US or India or the intention to affirm leadership, like in Rwanda or Morocco (Witter S. et al. 2016). Policies that are highly politicalised are subject to political volatility and therefore less likely to endure in the long term. This is the case for example in Mexico or the US, where social reforms or SRH- and gender equality-related policies have recently suffered from polarised political contexts and government changes. Where policies are led by ideology and part of a country's larger commitment to social reforms, like in Thailand or Rwanda, they are more likely to be sustainable and enhanced over time. Because such reforms may also commit to address health inequities comprehensively, they are also more likely to adopt effective intersectional approaches.

Another governance factor that was found to play a critical role is social participation. The WHO defines social participation as “empowering people, communities, and civil society through inclusive participation in decision-making processes that affect health across the policy cycle and at all levels of the system” (Koch et al. 2024) and adopted in 2024 a resolution that recognises the importance of social participation for achieving UHC (World Health Organization 2024b). Results of this review greatly confirm the importance of involving civil society, NGOs, communities and community groups, including women’s groups for the design, implementation and governance of health financing policies and programmes if they are to effectively address gender inequities. Across all examples discussed in the review, social participation was found to support the design of more gender-equitable benefit packages, eligibility and enrolment criteria, to ensure broad uptake and utilisation of the schemes by supporting adequate outreach to vulnerable women with tailored communication and awareness efforts and community-based engagements, and to contribute to addressing social and cultural norms preventing women from accessing care. Civil society helped generate and leverage evidence to improve existing policies in programmes.

Social participation also contributes to governments and health system’s social accountability, for example as is the case of Thailand, where civil society is an integral pillar of the health system and UCS governance (World Health Organization 2021). While accountability mechanisms can bring policy changes and help ensure programmes deliver on their intended outcomes, especially as gender equality is not only an integral part of the SDGs, but also a fundamental human right as set out in the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights, there is still limited evidence of their potential in the context of UHC (Ravindran and Govender 2020).

It was found that the role that civil society and local communities can play is also impacted by gendered cultural and social norms. In India, the ASHAs have been a strategic and successful pillar for JSY implementation and more broadly the health system’s ability to reach women. However, as female community health

workers, they have suffered from poor remuneration, recognition and respect by formal health workers and the government, and their political protest for better working conditions was met with scepticism in India, including at community level (Ved et al. 2019; Dasgupta et al. 2022). This perpetuates and contributes to largely recognised inequalities between male and female health workers in terms of pay, employment security and workplace violence. This entails that the role of civil society and communities is largely dependent on local cultural norms and the government's will and ability to influence them. The review confirms however that social participation, which can come in many forms depending on the context of the policies and programmes, plays a critical role in generating evidence and awareness on gender inequalities in health financing and UHC, and in addressing them. The resolution adopted at the World Health Assembly in 2024 endorses this finding and should support the further development of participatory spaces and programmes as well as associated accountability and reporting mechanisms.

The review also found that whether some policies and programmes' features address or perpetuate gender disparities could also be discussed. For example, the decision to make women the main recipients of CCT programmes like Mexico's Oportunidades or voluntary health insurance schemes, including microinsurance, may be founded on the intent to leverage intra-household gendered roles rather than changing them (Banthia et al. 2009; International Finance Corporation and AXA 2015; Finnoff 2016). Several papers (Bradshaw 2008; Gamarnik 2020; Finnoff 2016) argue that targeting women is based on the assumption that they put their household's needs before theirs, compared to men, and are therefore more likely to enrol and adhere to the programme. Obligations imposed by the health financing programme, like Oportunidades, may in fact reinforce the burden and responsibility put on women and further de-responsibilise men, perpetuating gender stereotypes (Radel et al. 2017). As outlined in this review, such health financing mechanisms can positively impact women's empowerment and control of financial resources, but more evidence is needed on whether they do contribute to addressing the root causes of health financing inequities in the long term.

Generally, evidence that DSF mechanisms or voluntary insurance schemes – including the publicly-funded ones – have indeed helped address the inequities they were created to tackle was found to be rather mixed: they can positively reduce OOP and catastrophic spending, but on their own are not enough to avoid women foregoing care and major non-financial barriers remain, such as distance to facilities or intra-household, community and provider-patient relations (Witter et al. 2017; Ravindran 2012). While assessing how successful health financing policies and programmes effectively are at addressing gender inequities and their root causes was not the objective of this review, some findings are worth considering from a contextual factor perspective.

One consistent finding across the reviewed studies is that health financing policies and programmes on their own are not enough to address the known gender inequities that achieving UHC should tackle. Another main finding is that very few policies and programmes seem to have been implemented with this consideration, despite the existing literature from the past fifteen years (Sen et al. 2007; World Health Organization 2009, 2010a; The World Bank 2011; Sen et al. 2021), that is by being adopted as part of at least health-system-wide, and at best cross-sectoral approaches. Policies and programmes have often been implemented in a fragmented and uncoordinated way which hinder the impact they can have and progress towards gender equality and UHC.

For example, in many countries in Africa and Asia, including India, SRH services are not covered, or very insufficiently, by government-sponsored insurance schemes, because they have historically been funded and delivered through vertical, standalone programmes, such as DSF (Holtz and Sarker 2018). The co-existence of DSF mechanisms in parallel to insurance schemes, but also the co-existence of multiple insurance schemes such as CBHI or PFHIS, with varying eligibility criteria, results in the fragmentation of the pooling function. Yet, this fragmentation is more costly for health systems, results in higher reliance on OOP for women, hinder progress towards UHC and ultimately, does not reduce and even perpetuate inequities across different population segments (Holtz and Sarker 2018; Ravindran and Govender 2020). Gender-specific DSF programmes

that are better integrated into or at least coordinated with national UHC strategies, like Mexico's Prospera, India's JSY and Nepal's SDIP were found to be more sustainable (Witter and Somanathan 2012), though as previously discussed, major disparities remain.

This raises the question of how adequate gender-specific policies and programmes like DSF, which can reinforce health financing systems' fragmentation, are to contribute towards equity and UHC? It could be argued that such programmes are an effective way to proactively tackle inequities in the absence of mandatory UHC schemes and in already-fragmented financing systems, like in India. However, even though many Latin American countries have achieved nearly universal coverage with publicly-funded insurance schemes and include comprehensive SRH in their benefit packages, barriers still exist for some women and many of those countries still have large-scale DSF schemes like CCT in place (Holtz and Sarker 2018). In the case of Mexico, positive synergies were found between Prospera and Seguro Popular in reducing coverage gaps (Serván-Mori et al. 2019) and the elimination of Prospera before the COVID pandemic was found to have contributed to an increase in poverty during that period (Knaul et al. 2023). Countries like Thailand on the other hand, can rely simply on their national UHC scheme (in combination, like many other health systems worldwide, with employment-based schemes) to deliver equitable access to services like SRH. Factors of differential implementation are therefore likely outside of the health financing system, which, as already outlined in the review results, confirms that policy coordination across the health system blocks and even beyond is critical.

Non-financial factors that are consistently found to contribute to the success of health financing policies or programmes in tackling gender inequities are associated to the health system performance and social determinants of health. Evidence largely shows that supply-side factors, like the quality and extent of the healthcare delivery system or adequate investments in the workforce significantly influence women's ability to benefit from financial protection schemes and access care (Appleford et al. 2020). This is a key finding for policy-makers and provides

actionable recommendations for health system performance. The intersection of gender with other social determinants of health like socio-economic status, education, location, ethnicity or religion has also been recognised as a differential factor of access to care without financial hardship among women within a similar context. The review found that health financing policies and programmes that are most successful at improving gender equality are those that are complemented by policies and programmes working towards addressing those other factors. One initial hypothesis was that this should happen in an intentional, coordinated way. However, findings from the review could not confirm this theory.

The reviewed studies discuss different contexts. The implementation of several policies and programmes was directly complemented by supply-side interventions such as investment in infrastructure and workforce development and education, purchasing and incentive strategies, as well as various tailored, community-level awareness and educational efforts aimed at addressing social and cultural barriers (World Bank 2007; Frenk et al. 2012; Witter and Ensor op. 2012; Appleford et al. 2020). Those coordinated and intersectional approaches, while often found insufficient, did contribute to improving women's equitable access to care. It is interesting to note that in some cases, it was evidence of the weaknesses of the scheme's initial phase that informed the need to implement those additional efforts (Rahmawati et al. 2024; Dubey et al. 2023). This shows the importance of having performance evaluation processes in place, though the review also found that the evidence could also come from civil society and NGOs (Rahmawati et al. 2024).

In other cases, health financing policies and programmes are implemented in contexts that already demonstrate a good performance in terms of gender equality, for health status or women's status in society overall, like Rwanda, India's southern states or Thailand. There is a large body of literature that associate higher levels of women's empowerment, education, employment and representation with better health outcomes (Plouffe V. et al. 2020; World Health Organization 2010a; The World Bank 2011; Hellwig and Barros 2022); and indeed, the review consistently found that education or employment were critical

factors perpetuating inequities among women and between women and men in their ability to access and benefit from financial protection for health. Those are long-term societal changes and beyond the scope of health financing policies only, even within a UHC context. It could therefore be argued that a women's more equal status in society is a "pre-requisite" for health financing policies to effectively tackle remaining inequities.

One can then ask what would be considered a good threshold for gender equality and what would be the indicators? Indices like the Gender Inequality Index (GII) generally use dimensions such as reproductive health, education, employment and female representation at parliament to assess a country's gender equality performance (United Nations 2024). Like Rwanda or Kerala, studies have argued that Bangladesh has achieved remarkable performance in health indicators such as maternal mortality ratio despite economic poverty due to its commitment to social development and gender equality and a higher representation of women in government functions compared to their peers (Chowdhury et al. 2013).

However, as discussed in the case of Rwanda (USAID 2014) or Kerala (RamPrakash and Lingam 2021), higher government representation of women and performance in maternal health indicators does not automatically translate in sustained higher utilisation of healthcare services beyond SRH and reduced OOP spending. First, as the review also showed, maternal health is one area that has largely benefited from vertical programmes, often heavily donor-funded, and is not representative of a country's broader gender-equitable UHC performance. Furthermore, in those regions, social and cultural norms impeding women's empowerment remain prevalent and contribute to perpetuating gender inequities in access to health (USAID 2014; RamPrakash and Lingam 2021; Evans 2020; O'Connell et al. 2015). A recommendation for additional research would be to assess the impact of higher female representation in government – notably in Ministries of Health and Finance – on more gender-equitable UHC as well as to understand how policy development processes that address gender inequities look like.

Health systems are social and political institutions that reflect inequities in societies (Cerceanu 2012). At the same time, structural changes in society get reflected at the institutional level and directly impact health systems, including policies and attitudes, such as healthcare-seeking behaviours or healthcare workers' status and behaviours (Ravindran and Gaitonde 2018). This implies that while health financing policies on their own can only do so much to change social norms that influence their performance, policy-makers should more actively acknowledge and consider those contextual factors when designing and implementing policies and programmes and look to influence sustained structural changes (Heymann et al. 2019).

While there certainly is an association between a country's socio-economic development and how gender-equitable their health financing system is (United Nations 2024), there is an opportunity for further research. For example, Thailand ranks 84th at the GII, is not a high-income country as per the World Bank's definition and yet, has achieved remarkable gender equality in their UHC scheme. Interestingly, as discussed in the review, there is little evidence on the gender implications of the Thai's health system and UHC scheme; it is assumed that gender is one equity dimension that improves as social determinants of health are comprehensively addressed towards UHC. Rwanda, Bangladesh and Kerala demonstrate that economic development is not a pre-requisite for good social development. The connection between a country's social – including gender – and economic development and gender-equitable health financing system is one area that deserves further research.

Like Thailand's case, there is limited evidence on the gender implications of most high-income countries' health financing and UHC systems. The review included all economies in the research scope, yet LMICs are overrepresented in the results. While there is a good body of literature on gender inequities in health in European countries or other high-income countries worldwide, most is not related to health financing specifically and therefore not in scope for this review. One paper argues that there is no country in the world systematically applying a gender lens to its UHC system (Rodin 2013). Another reason for the lack of

additional literature may be that in the context of gender mainstreaming, countries are adopting gender-transformative policies along with policies tackling other social determinants of health, and those policies together are cutting across multiple health system blocks. Health financing is thus not explicitly called out. Literature argues that this is in fact desirable (World Health Organization 2010a; Sen et al. 2021). One of this review's key theory which was largely confirmed is that indeed, gender inequities require a health-system wide approach to be effectively addressed, even from a financing perspective only. Health financing policies are more effective when other health system blocks' gender performance is also improving – or has already improved.

This brings to one of the limitations of this study. The research's focus on health financing policies and programmes, furthermore on evidence of a positive impact on gender inequities, means that other areas, when they did not explicitly refer to health financing mechanisms, were excluded. This includes for example literature on gender-mainstreaming policies; gender inequities in other health system blocks such as workforce or governance; gender inequities in science and health research or inequities in health financing and towards UHC but not related to gender specifically. While the realist review methodology means that some literature was ultimately considered even if it did not directly match the selection criteria, this combined focus on health financing and gender implies that literature related more largely to intersectionality or multisectoral approaches was not included.

As already outlined, the research led to a large body of literature that defined gender inequities in health financing across multiple geographies, but with no evidence or discussion of policies or programmes that worked, and even less on the contextual factors behind them, leading to their exclusion. While some articles were reconsidered after the initial search identified countries and types of interventions to focus on, because of saturation it was not possible to assess all the literature that merely confirmed the evidence of gender inequities in health financing and UHC. It may be assumed that some studies could help provide additional information to the questions discussed here.

A recommendation for further research on this topic would be to take a geography-based approach (such as one country or region or a selection of countries or regions) and take a health-system wide or multi-sectoral approach to policies and programmes aiming to improve gender equality in health, or take an intersectional approach to policies and programmes aiming to address inequities towards UHC.

Furthermore, a lot of the research found focused essentially on SRH, and specifically maternal health. The keywords used in the research such as UHC and gender led to a large amount of literature focused on SRH, among which few discussing gender inequities. The vast majority of DSF mechanisms have been focusing on SRH, and maternal health and are therefore gender-specific programmes targeting women; however, papers that did not address gender inequities or that discussed SRH policies and programmes and their gender implications without a health financing lens were initially excluded. Some were reconsidered later for their richness, that is their ability to provide relevant information for the theory testing, but it may also be assumed here that a deeper dive on SRH may provide further insights on gender inequities.

The evidence found on gender implications of the purchasing function was essentially focused on DSF mechanisms and SRH services. This is another limitation of the study, which is caused by the bias of the literature where gender inequities in health financing are overly represented by gender-specific interventions for SRH services. The implementation of providers' financial incentives and purchasing strategies to address critical gender inequities at delivery and workforce level was found to be an important factor contributing to the success of a gender-specific intervention or not (Appleford et al. 2020; Witter and Ensor op. 2012; Basinga et al. 2010). As the literature shows that provider-patient relations are a major barrier to financial protection scheme utilisation beyond SRH (Ravindran 2012; Witter et al. 2017; RamPrakash and Lingam 2021), we could hypothesize that such incentives and purchasing strategies could certainly apply to other health areas and encourage policymakers to more

actively apply a gender lens to in the purchasing function of the financing system and its interventions.

A recommendation for policy-makers would be to consider applying the positive learnings of gender-specific DSF mechanisms beyond their usual SRH scope. As evidence largely shows the higher and increasing morbidity of women compared to men, in all countries and across a broad range of diseases and the differential sex-related health needs, and as women are more likely to risk financial catastrophe from care beyond SRH too (Crimmins et al. 2011; Ginsburg et al. 2023; Criado-Perez 2019), it may be worth considering whether targeted gender-specific health financing interventions could apply to areas such as mental health, cancer and other chronic diseases, menopause and other sex-related health needs.

More broadly, there is a large opportunity for policy-makers to actively consider women's differential health needs beyond SRH. The review found that most health financing and UHC policies and programmes aiming to address gender inequities, as well as more generally the metrics used to measure performance from a gender perspective relate to SRH. The review showed however that the large, pervasive and persisting inequities affecting women's ability to utilise health services without suffering from financial hardship extend largely beyond SRH services. While, as discussed, intersectional approaches and a longstanding focus on tackling socio-economic disparities have contributed to better provide coverage for vulnerable women, many women are left uncovered by existing financial protection schemes. For example, "missing middle" women who do not benefit from employment-based insurance schemes because they are not formally employed or married to a formal workers, nor are eligible to enrol to a universal, tax-revenue-based scheme targeting the poorest and most vulnerable (Witter et al. 2017; Ravindran 2012; Sharma et al. 2023). This means that policy-makers cannot simply rely on efforts to tackle other inequities: gender equality should be a standalone part of their agenda.

This is certainly a general recommendation that has consistently been made over the past two decades and which, as demonstrated, remains largely to be taken

up. However, it can be reformulated with another recommendation for which the evidence is growing: policy-makers should actively address gender inequalities in health, including in health financing, because it is not only the right thing to do to fulfil their commitment to UHC, but because it also contributes to economic growth – and of relevance for the private sector, financial growth. A growing body of literature demonstrates that not only gender equality and better health outcomes for women contributes to sustainable development (The World Bank 2011; Langer et al. 2015), but there is also a strong business case and short-term-gain opportunity for both public and private sectors for investing in women’s health, which should appeal to political will and call for strengthened cross-sectoral collaboration in this area (IFC et al. 2015; World Health Organization 2020; World Economic Forum and McKinsey Health Institute 2024).

Conclusions

This realist review sought to understand the requirements for addressing gender inequities in health financing towards achieving UHC. Applying a gender lens to health financing policies and programmes, the review analysed a diverse range of geographies and intervention types and identified several contextual factors that support their success in increasing gender equality.

The review confirmed that intentionally applying a gender perspective when designing and implementing health financing policies and programmes, by recognising women's differential needs and barriers to access care and including tailored approaches to address them, is critical. Whether it's a tax-revenue-based UHC scheme, a publicly-funded or a private insurance scheme or another financing mechanism like DSF, women, especially women from the poorest and most vulnerable population segments, will always be less likely to enrol, benefit and utilise a financial protection scheme compared to men, unless measures are adopted to prevent or, at the minimum, mitigate those disparities. Measures include gender-sensitive eligibility and enrolment criteria and methods, equitable premium rating and subsidies and tailored outreach and awareness approaches. Benefit packages should be explicit and comprehensive, focusing on meeting women's primary healthcare needs through their lifecycle, including but not limited to SRH.

Importantly, those policies and programmes should be complemented, or preceded, by efforts and investments to strengthen the health system performance across other building blocks, especially improving the capacity and quality of healthcare delivery, considering the infrastructure and the workforce.

While efforts to tackle inequities at large, especially income- and location-based disparities may contribute to reduce gender inequities, the review found that this will almost always be insufficient. This is because gender inequities are driven by deeply rooted social and cultural norms that influence women's access to quality care across many aspects of society and the health system. While societal changes take time and are beyond the unique scope of health financing systems, the review found that some factors can contribute to a meaningful and sustained

impact of health financing reforms on women's ability to access quality care. Although volatile, political will was identified as a key enabler. Social participation emerged as equally critical; engaging local communities and civil society throughout policy and programme design and implementation helps address the determinants that affect women's healthcare access. It also sustains government's commitment and accountability and can contribute to maintain or activate political will throughout political cycles. Social participation is essential to ensuring that interventions are sensitive to local norms and foster the trust among women and their relatives and communities needed to drive change in behaviours.

Interestingly, the review found more contextual factors explaining why health financing interventions and UHC systems are still failing at addressing gender inequities than how they can effectively succeed. As countries are progressing towards UHC and as momentum and evidence is building towards gender-equitable access to health, there is an opportunity for policy-makers and other health financing stakeholders to recognise, leverage and further demonstrate that addressing gender disparities is an investment that gives an incredibly valuable social, economic and financial return.

Appendices

Table 2. Studies selected during the initial search

	Author(s)	Title	Year	Intervention type	Focus on SRH	Country
1	Ahmed S., Khan M.M.	A maternal health voucher scheme: What have we learned from the demand-side financing scheme in Bangladesh?	2011	Voucher	Yes	Bangladesh
2	Appleford G; RamaRao S; Bellows B	The inclusion of sexual and reproductive health services within universal health care through intentional design	2020	Purchasing, multiple interventions. Incl CCT	Yes	Multiple. Includes Mexico, Thailand, India
3	Balasubramanian P., Ravindran T.K.S.	Pro-poor maternity benefit schemes and rural women findings from Tamil Nadu	2012	CCT	Yes	India
4	Banthia A., Johnson S., McCord M.J., Mathews B.	Microinsurance that works for women: Making gender-sensitive microinsurance programs	2009	Microinsurance	No	Multiple. Includes India
5	Barber, Sarah L.; Gertler, Paul J.	Empowering women to obtain high quality care: evidence from an evaluation of Mexico's conditional cash transfer programme	2009	CCT	Yes	Mexico
6	Cerceau S.	Gender equality in access to health care: The role of social health protection	2012	Publicly-funded health insurance scheme	No	India
7	De Allegri M., Ridde V., Louis V.R., Sarker M., Tiendrebéogo J., Yé M., Müller O., Jahn A.	Determinants of utilisation of maternal care services after the reduction of user fees: A case study from rural Burkina Faso	2011	Abolition of user fees	Yes	Burkina Faso
8	Hellwig F; Barros AJ	Learning from success cases: ecological analysis of potential pathways to universal access to family planning care in low- and middle-income countries	2022	Health system reforms	Yes	Egypt, Ethiopia, Rwanda, Afghanistan, Brazil and Ecuador
9	Lim S.S., Dandona L., Hoisington J.A., James S.L., Hogan M.C., Gakidou E.	India's Janani Suraksha Yojana, a conditional cash transfer programme to increase births in health facilities: an impact evaluation	2010	CCT	Yes	India
10	Parkhurst J.O., Penn-Kekana L., Blaauw D., Balabanova D., Danishevski K., Rahman S.A., Onama V., Ssengooba F.	Health systems factors influencing maternal health services: A four-country comparison	2005	Multiple	Yes	Bangladesh, Russia, South Africa, and Uganda

11	Parmar D; De Allegri M; Savadogo G; Sauerborn R	Do community-based health insurance schemes fulfil the promise of equity? A study from Burkina Faso	2014	CBHI	No	Burkina Faso
12	Plouffe V; Bicaba F; Bicaba A; Druetz T	User fee policies and women's empowerment: a systematic scoping review	2020	Abolition of user fees	Not focus, discussed	Burkina Faso, Mali, Sierra Leone, Kenya, India
13	Rahmawati T., Hsieh H.-M.	Appraisal of universal health insurance and maternal health services utilization: pre- and post-context of the Jaminan Kesehatan Nasional implementation in Indonesia	2024	UHC	Yes	Indonesia
14	Rahmawati T., Hsieh H.-M., Liang F.-W.	Inequalities in women's health insurance coverage before and after the implementation of universal health insurance in Indonesia	2024	UHC	No	Indonesia
15	Ravindran TKS; Govender V	Sexual and reproductive health services in universal health coverage: a review of recent evidence from low- and middle-income countries	2020	Multiple	Yes	Multiple. Includes India, Mexico
16	Ravindran, TKS	Universal access: making health systems work for women	2012	Multiple	Not focus, discussed	Multiple. Includes Mexico, Thailand, India
17	Sharma SK; Nambiar D; Sankar H; Joseph J; Surendran S; Benny G	Gender-specific inequalities in coverage of Publicly Funded Health Insurance Schemes in Southern States of India: evidence from National Family Health Surveys	2023	Publicly-funded health insurance scheme	No	India
18	Witter S., Boukhalifa C., Cresswell J.A., Daou Z., Filippi V., Ganaba R., Goufodji S., Lange I.L., Marchal B., Richard F.	Cost and impact of policies to remove and reduce fees for obstetric care in Benin, Burkina Faso, Mali and Morocco	2016	Abolition of user fees	Yes	Benin, Burkina Faso, Mali and Morocco
19	Witter S., Ensor T.	Financing maternity care	2012	Multiple	Yes	Multiple
20	Witter S., Somanathan A.	Demand-Side Financing for Sexual and Reproductive Health Services in Low and Middle-Income Countries: A Review of the Evidence	2012	Multiple	Yes	Multiple. Includes India, Mexico, Bangladesh
21	Witter, Sophie; Govender, Veloshnee; Ravindran, T. K. Sundari; Yates, Robert	Minding the gaps: health financing, universal health coverage and gender	2017	Multiple	Not focus, discussed	Multiple. Includes India, Mexico, Thailand
22	Ziegler, S.; Srivastava, S.; Parmar, D.; Basu, S.; Jain, N.; De Allegri, M	A step closer towards achieving universal health coverage: the role of gender in enrolment in health insurance in India	2024	Publicly-funded health insurance scheme	No	India

References

2000-2015, Millennium Development Goals. Research Guides: UN Documentation: Development (2024). Available online at <https://research.un.org/en/docs/dev/2000-2015>, updated on 10/7/2024, checked on 10/7/2024.

Ahmed S., Khan M.M. (2011): A maternal health voucher scheme: What have we learned from the demand-side financing scheme in Bangladesh? In *02681080* 26 (1). DOI: 10.1093/heapol/czq015.

Appleford, G; RamaRao, S; Bellows, B (2020): The inclusion of sexual and reproductive health services within universal health care through intentional design. In *Sexual and reproductive health matters* 28 (2), p. 1799589. DOI: 10.1080/26410397.2020.1799589.

Azad, Ameer D.; Charles, Anthony G.; Ding, Qian; Trickey, Amber W.; Wren, Sherry M. (2020): The gender gap and healthcare: associations between gender roles and factors affecting healthcare access in Central Malawi, June-August 2017. In *Archives of public health = Archives belges de sante publique* 78 (1), p. 119. DOI: 10.1186/s13690-020-00497-w.

Balasubramanian P., Ravindran T.K.S. (2012): Pro-poor maternity benefit schemes and rural women findings from Tamil Nadu. In *00129976* 47 (25).

Banthia, A; Johnson, S.; McCord, M.J.; Mathews, B. (2009): Microinsurance that works for women: Making gender-sensitive microinsurance programs. Geneva (Microinsurance paper no.3).

Barber, Sarah L.; Gertler, Paul J. (2009): Empowering women to obtain high quality care: evidence from an evaluation of Mexico's conditional cash transfer programme. In *02681080* 24 (1), pp. 18–25. DOI: 10.1093/heapol/czn039.

Baru; Acharya; Acharya; Shiva Kumar; Nagaraj (2010): Inequities in access to health services in India: Caste, class and region. In *Economic and Political Weekly* 45 (38), pp. 49–58. Available online at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/289058749_Inequities_in_access_to_health_services_in_India_Caste_class_and_region.

Basinga, Paulin; Gertler, Paul J.; Binagwaho, Agnes; Soucat, Agnes L.B.; Sturdy, Jennifer R.; Vermeersch, Christel M.J. (2010): Paying primary health care centers for performance in Rwanda. In *Policy Research Working Paper Series*. Available online at <https://ideas.repec.org/p/wbk/wbrwps/5190.html>.

Baum, Fran; Musolino, Connie; Gesesew, Hailay Abrha; Popay, Jennie (2021): New Perspective on Why Women Live Longer Than Men: An Exploration of Power, Gender, Social Determinants, and Capitals. In *International journal of environmental research and public health* 18 (2). DOI: 10.3390/ijerph18020661.

Borah, Pradip (2019): A brief study on the gender inequality in North East India. In *Journal of Critical Reviews* 06 (03). Available online at <https://www.jcreview.com/admin/Uploads/Files/623172a3e11a05.34269463.pdf>, checked on 10/25/2024.

Bradshaw, Sarah (2008): From Structural Adjustment to Social Adjustment. In *Global Social Policy* 8 (2), pp. 188–207. DOI: 10.1177/1468018108090638.

Cerceau, S (2012): Gender equality in access to health care: How social health protection can tackle access barriers for women and improve gender-related inequities. A case study on India's national health insurance scheme Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana (RSBY). Internship Placement: Indo German Social Security Programme, GIZ India. Available online at <https://documentation.ehesp.fr/memoires/2012/mph/cerceau.pdf>.

Chandoevrit, Worawan; Phatchana, Phasith (2019): Addressing the male-biased gender health gap. Thailand Development Research Institute. Available online at <https://tdri.or.th/en/2019/03/addressing-the-male-biased-gender-health-gap/>, updated on 3/28/2019, checked on 10/16/2024.

Chemouni, Benjamin (2018): The political path to universal health coverage: Power, ideas and community-based health insurance in Rwanda. In *World Development* 106, pp. 87–98. DOI: 10.1016/j.worlddev.2018.01.023.

Chirwa, GC; Moreno-Serra, R; Suhrcke, M (2021): Socioeconomic inequality in premiums for a community-based health insurance scheme in Rwanda. In *Health policy and planning* 36 (1), pp. 14–25. DOI: 10.1093/heapol/czaa135.

Chowdhury, AM; Bhuiya A; Chowdhury ME; Rasheed S; Hussain Z; Chen LC (2013): The Bangladesh paradox: exceptional health achievement despite economic poverty. In *Lancet (London, England)* 382 (9906), pp. 1734–1745. DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62148-0.

Criado-Perez, C. (2019): *Invisible women. Exposing data bias in a world designed for men* / Caroline Criado Perez. London: Vintage Digital.

Crimmins, Eileen M.; Kim, Jung Ki; Solé-Auró, Aïda (2011): Gender differences in health: results from SHARE, ELSA and HRS. In *Eur J Public Health* 21 (1), pp. 81–91. DOI: 10.1093/eurpub/ckq022.

Dada, Sara; Dalkin, Sonia; Gilmore, Brynne; Hunter, Rebecca; Mukumbang, Ferdinand C. (2023): Applying and reporting relevance, richness and rigour in realist evidence appraisals: Advancing key concepts in realist reviews. In *Research Synthesis Methods* 14 (3), pp. 504–514. DOI: 10.1002/jrsm.1630.

Dasgupta, Jashodhara; Sinha, Dipa; Joshi, Deepika (2022): Interrogating the position of ASHAs, the community health workers in India. A cog in the health system or a social activist? *Medicus Mundi Schweiz (MMS Bulletin #162, 162)*. Available online at <https://www.medicusmundi.ch/de/advocacy/publikationen/mms-bulletin/community-health-workers-and-health-systems-s/kapitel-4/a-cog-in-the-health-system-or-a-social-activi>, updated on 10/18/2024, checked on 10/18/2024.

De Allegri, M; Ridde V.; Louis V.R.; Sarker M.; Tiendrebéogo J.; Yé M. et al. (2011): Determinants of utilisation of maternal care services after the reduction of user fees: A case study from rural Burkina Faso. In *01688510* 99 (3). DOI: 10.1016/j.healthpol.2010.10.010.

Devi, K.R. Lakshmy (2012): Education, health and women's empowerment - Kerala's experience in linking the triad. Available online at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/293612239_Education_health_and_women's_empowerment_-_Kerala's_experience_in_linking_the_triad.

Dubey, S; Deshpande, S; Krishna, L; Zadey, S (2023): Evolution of Government-funded health insurance for universal health coverage in India. In *The Lancet regional health. Southeast Asia* 13, p. 100180. DOI: 10.1016/j.lansea.2023.100180.

Dupas, P.; Jain, R. (2021): Women Left Behind: Gender Disparities in Utilization of Government Health Insurance in India. NBER Working Paper No. w28972.

Ensor, Tim; Bhatt, Hema; Tiwari, Suresh (2017): Incentivizing universal safe delivery in Nepal: 10 years of experience. In *Health Policy Plan* 32 (8), pp. 1185–1192. DOI: 10.1093/heapol/czx070.

Evans, Alice (2020): Why do women in South India have more freedom than their northern sisters? In *Scroll.in*, 10/12/2020. Available online at <https://scroll.in/article/975151/why-do-women-in-south-india-have-more-freedom-than-their-northern-sisters>, checked on 10/25/2024.

Finnoff, Kade (2016): Gender Disparity in Access to the Rwandan Mutual Health Insurance Scheme. In *Feminist Economics* 22 (3), pp. 26–50. DOI: 10.1080/13545701.2015.1088658.

Freedman, Vicki A.; Wolf, Douglas A.; Spillman, Brenda C. (2016): Disability-Free Life Expectancy Over 30 Years: A Growing Female Disadvantage in the US Population. In *American journal of public health* 106 (6), pp. 1079–1085. DOI: 10.2105/AJPH.2016.303089.

Frenk, Julio; Gómez-Dantés, Octavio; Langer, Ana (2012): A comprehensive approach to women's health: lessons from the Mexican health reform. In *BMC women's health* 12 (1), p. 42. DOI: 10.1186/1472-6874-12-42.

Gamarnik, Jessica Lynn (2020): Empowerment through Poverty Policy: The Evolution of Conditional Cash Transfer Programs in Mexico. Carleton University, Ottawa, Ontario. Available online at <https://repository.library.carleton.ca/downloads/s1784m755>.

Ginsburg, Ophira; Vanderpuye, Verna; Beddoe, Ann Marie; Bhoo-Pathy, Nirmala; Bray, Freddie; Caduff, Carlo et al. (2023): Women, power, and cancer:

a Lancet Commission. In *Lancet (London, England)* 402 (10417), pp. 2113–2166. DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(23)01701-4.

Govender, V.; Ataguba, J.E.; Alaba, O.A. (2014): Health insurance coverage within households: The case of private health insurance in South Africa. In *10185895* 39 (4). DOI: 10.1057/gpp.2014.29.

Gupta, Adyya; Fledderjohann, Jasmine; Reddy, Hanimi; Raman, V. R.; Stuckler, David; Vellakkal, Sukumar (2018): Barriers and prospects of India's conditional cash transfer program to promote institutional delivery care: a qualitative analysis of the supply-side perspectives. In *14726963* 18 (1), p. 40. DOI: 10.1186/s12913-018-2849-8.

Gwatkin, Davidson R.; Ergo, Alex (2011): Universal health coverage: friend or foe of health equity? In *Lancet (London, England)* 377 (9784), pp. 2160–2161. DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(10)62058-2.

Heise, L.; Greene, M.E.; Opper, N.; Stavropoulou, M.; Harper, C.; Nascimento, M.; Zewdie, D. (2019): Gender inequality and restrictive gender norms: framing the challenges to health 393 (10189). DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(19)30652-X.

Hellwig, F; Barros, AJ (2022): Learning from success cases: ecological analysis of potential pathways to universal access to family planning care in low- and middle-income countries. In *Gates open research* 6, p. 59. DOI: 10.12688/gatesopenres.13570.3.

Heymann, Jody; Levy, Jessica K.; Bose, Bijetri; Ríos-Salas, Vanessa; Mekonen, Yehualashet; Swaminathan, Hema et al. (2019): Improving health with programmatic, legal, and policy approaches to reduce gender inequality and change restrictive gender norms. In *Lancet (London, England)* 393 (10190), pp. 2522–2534. DOI: 10.1016/s0140-6736(19)30656-7.

Holtz, Jeanna; Sarker, Intissar (2018): Integrating Family Planning into Universal Health Coverage Efforts. USAID. Available online at <https://shopsplusproject.org/sites/default/files/resources/Integrating%20Family%20Planning%20into%20Universal%20Health%20Coverage%20Efforts.pdf>, checked on 10/20/2024.

Huang, Shan; Salm, Martin (2020): The effect of a ban on gender-based pricing on risk selection in the German health insurance market. In *Health economics* 29 (1), pp. 3–17. DOI: 10.1002/hec.3958.

Hunter, Benjamin M.; Murray, Susan F. (2017): Demand-side financing for maternal and newborn health: what do we know about factors that affect implementation of cash transfers and voucher programmes? In *BMC pregnancy and childbirth* 17 (1), p. 262. DOI: 10.1186/s12884-017-1445-y.

Ibáñez X.A., Garita A. (2015): Commentary: Mexico: Moving from universal health coverage towards health care for all. In *17441692* 10 (2). DOI: 10.1080/17441692.2014.986168.

IFC; AXA; Accenture (2015): SHEforSHIELD: Insure Women to Better Protect All. IFC. Available online at <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/228381492593824450/pdf/114402-WP-SheforShield-Final-Web2015-PUBLIC.pdf>.

International Finance Corporation and AXA (2015): SHEforSHIELD: Insure women to better protect all. IFC. Washington DC. Available online at <https://www.ifc.org/content/dam/ifc/doc/mgrt-pub/sheforshield-final-web2015.pdf>, checked on 10/28/2024.

Jagosh, Justin (2019): Realist Synthesis for Public Health: Building an Ontologically Deep Understanding of How Programs Work, For Whom, and In Which Contexts. In *Annual review of public health* 40, pp. 361–372. DOI: 10.1146/annurev-publhealth-031816-044451.

Jakarta Globe (2024): National Health Insurance JKN Coverage Reaches 98.19 Pct. Available online at <https://jakartaglobe.id/special-updates/national-health-insurance-jkn-coverage-reaches-9819-pct>, updated on 10/21/2024, checked on 10/21/2024.

Jamison, Dean T.; Summers, Lawrence H.; Alleyne, George; Arrow, Kenneth J.; Berkley, Seth; Binagwaho, Agnes et al. (2013): Global health 2035: a world converging within a generation. In *Lancet (London, England)* 382 (9908), pp. 1898–1955. DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62105-4.

Jejeebhoy, Shireen J.; Sathar, Zeba A. (2001): Women's Autonomy in India and Pakistan: The Influence of Religion and Region. In *Population and Development Review* 27 (4), pp. 687–712. Available online at https://econpapers.repec.org/article/blapopdev/v_3a27_3ay_3a2001_3ai_3a4_3ap_3a687-712.htm.

Kaufman, M. R.; Eschliman, E. L.; Karver, T. S. (2023): Differentiating sex and gender in health research to achieve gender equity. In *Bulletin of the World Health Organization* 101 (10), pp. 666–671. DOI: 10.2471/BLT.22.289310.

Kawuki, Joseph; Gatasi, Ghislaine; Sserwanja, Quraish (2022): Women empowerment and health insurance utilisation in Rwanda: a nationwide cross-sectional survey. In *BMC women's health* 22 (1), p. 378. DOI: 10.1186/s12905-022-01976-8.

Kindig, David A.; Cheng, Erika R. (2013): Even as mortality fell in most US counties, female mortality nonetheless rose in 42.8 percent of counties from 1992 to 2006. In *Health affairs (Project Hope)* 32 (3), pp. 451–458. DOI: 10.1377/hlthaff.2011.0892.

Knaul, Felicia Marie; Arreola-Ornelas, Hector; Touchton, Michael; McDonald, Tim; Blofield, Merike; Avila Burgos, Leticia et al. (2023): Setbacks in the quest for universal health coverage in Mexico: polarised politics, policy upheaval, and pandemic disruption. In *The Lancet* 402 (10403), pp. 731–746. DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(23)00777-8.

Knaul F.M., Frenk J. (2005): Health insurance in Mexico: Achieving universal coverage through structural reform - A 2003 reform is making good progress toward covering Mexico's eleven million uninsured families by 2010. In *The Lancet* 24 (6). DOI: 10.1377/hlthaff.24.6.1467.

Koch, C; Dheepa, R; Brearley, L; Khalid, F (2024): Clarifying terms and concepts: what is meant by social participation in decision-making for health. In *Eurohealth* 30 (1). Available online at <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/376885/Eurohealth-30-1-11-18-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>, checked on 10/28/2024.

Kutzin, Joseph; Cashin, Cheryl; Jakab, Melitta (2010): Implementing Health Financing Reform: Lessons from countries in transition. World Health Organization. Available online at <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789289042116>.

Kutzin J. (2012): Anything goes on the path to universal health coverage? no. In *Bulletin of the World Health Organization* 90 (11). DOI: 10.2471/BLT.12.113654.

Langer, A.; Meleis, A.; Knaul, F. M.; Atun, R.; Aran, M.; Arreola-Ornelas, H. et al. (2015): Women and Health: the key for sustainable development. In *Lancet (London, England)* 386 (9999), pp. 1165–1210. DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(15)60497-4.

Lee, Lois K.; Chien, Alyna; Stewart, Amanda; Truschel, Larissa; Hoffmann, Jennifer; Portillo, Elyse et al. (2020): Women's Coverage, Utilization, Affordability, And Health After The ACA: A Review Of The Literature. In *Health affairs (Project Hope)* 39 (3), pp. 387–394. DOI: 10.1377/hlthaff.2019.01361.

Lim, S.S.; Dandona L.; Hoisington J.A.; James S.L.; Hogan M.C.; Gakidou E. (2010): India's Janani Suraksha Yojana, a conditional cash transfer programme to increase births in health facilities: an impact evaluation. In *01406736 375 (9730)*. DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(10)60744-1.

Limwattananon, Supon (2008): Equity in Financing Healthcare: Impact of Universal Access to Healthcare in Thailand. In *Working Papers*. Available online at <https://ideas.repec.org/p/ess/wpaper/id1577.html>.

Limwattananon, Supon; Tangcharoensathien, Viroj; Prakongsai, Phusit (2010): Equity in maternal and child health in Thailand. In *Bulletin of the World Health Organization* 88 (6), pp. 420–427. DOI: 10.2471/BLT.09.068791.

Moradhvaj; Saikia, Nandita (2019): Gender disparities in health care expenditures and financing strategies (HCFS) for inpatient care in India. In *SSM - population health* 9, p. 100372. DOI: 10.1016/j.ssmph.2019.100372.

Morgan, Rosemary; Ayiasi, Richard Mangwi; Barman, Debjani; Buzuzi, Stephen; Ssemugabo, Charles; Ezumah, Nkoli et al. (2018): Gendered health

systems: evidence from low- and middle-income countries. In *Health research policy and systems* 16 (1), p. 58. DOI: 10.1186/s12961-018-0338-5.

Nadella, Pranay; Subramanian, S. V.; Roman-Urrestarazu, Andres (2021): The impact of community health workers on antenatal and infant health in India: A cross-sectional study. In *SSM - population health* 15, p. 100872. DOI: 10.1016/j.ssmph.2021.100872.

Nanda P. (2002): Gender dimensions of user fees: Implications for women's utilization of health care. In *09688080* 10 (20). DOI: 10.1016/S0968-8080(02)00083-6.

Núñez, Paula Sevilla (2023): Mexico's 20-year conditional cash transfer program supports low-income households to access services. *Pathfinders. SDG16+*. Available online at <https://www.sdg16.plus/policies/mexicos-20-year-conditional-cash-transfer-program-supports-low-income-households-to-access-services/>, updated on 7/11/2023, checked on 10/18/2024.

O'Connell, TS; Bedford, KJ; Thiede, M; McIntyre, D (2015): Synthesizing qualitative and quantitative evidence on non-financial access barriers: implications for assessment at the district level. In *International journal for equity in health* 14, p. 54. DOI: 10.1186/s12939-015-0181-z.

Onah, M.N.; Govender, V (2014): Out-of-pocket payments, health care access and utilisation in south-eastern Nigeria: A gender perspective. In *19326203* 9 (4). DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0093887.

PAHO (2021): Out-of-pocket expenditure in health. The need for a gender analysis. Pan-American Health Organisation. Washington, D.C.

Pan American Health Organization (2019): A Framework and Indicators for Monitoring Gender Equality and Health in the Americas. With assistance of Pan American Health Organization: Organización Panamericana de la Salud. Available online at <https://iris.paho.org/handle/10665.2/51786>.

Parkhurst J.O.; Penn-Kekana L.; Blaauw D.; Balabanova D.; Danishevski K.; Rahman S.A. et al. (2005): Health systems factors influencing maternal health

services: A four-country comparison. In *01688510 73* (2). DOI: 10.1016/j.healthpol.2004.11.001.

Parmar, D; De Allegri, M; Savadogo, G; Sauerborn, R (2014): Do community-based health insurance schemes fulfil the promise of equity? A study from Burkina Faso. In *Health policy and planning* 29 (1), pp. 76–84. DOI: 10.1093/heapol/czs136.

Pawson, Ray; Greenhalgh, Trisha; Harvey, Gill; Walshe, Kieran (2005): Realist review--a new method of systematic review designed for complex policy interventions. In *Journal of health services research & policy* 10 Suppl 1, pp. 21–34. DOI: 10.1258/1355819054308530.

Percival, Valerie; Dusabe-Richards, Esther; Wurie, Haja; Namakula, Justine; Ssali, Sarah; Theobald, Sally (2018): Are health systems interventions gender blind? examining health system reconstruction in conflict affected states. In *Globalization and health* 14 (1), p. 90. DOI: 10.1186/s12992-018-0401-6.

Percival, Valerie; Richards, Esther; MacLean, Tammy; Theobald, Sally (2014): Health systems and gender in post-conflict contexts: building back better? In *Confl Health* 8 (1), pp. 1–14. DOI: 10.1186/1752-1505-8-19.

Philip, NE; Ravindran, TKS (2017): Government sponsored health insurance coverage and out-of-pocket spending among elderly in Kerala: a cross-sectional study. In *JARH* 2 (1), pp. 9–21. DOI: 10.14302/issn.2474-7785.jarh-17-1489.

Plouffe V.; Bicaba F.; Bicaba A.; Druetz T. (2020): User fee policies and women's empowerment: a systematic scoping review. In *BMC health services research* 20 (1), p. 982. DOI: 10.1186/s12913-020-05835-w.

Quick, Jonathan; Jay, Jonathan; Langer, Ana (2014): Improving women's health through universal health coverage. In *PLoS medicine* 11 (1), e1001580. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1001580.

Radel, Claudia; Schmook, Birgit; Haenn, Nora; Green, Lisa (2017): The gender dynamics of conditional cash transfers and smallholder farming in Calakmul, Mexico. In *Women's Studies International Forum* 65, pp. 17–27. DOI: 10.1016/j.wsif.2016.06.004.

Rahmawati, T; Hsieh, H.-M. (2024): Appraisal of universal health insurance and maternal health services utilization: pre- and post-context of the Jaminan Kesehatan Nasional implementation in Indonesia. In *22962565* 12. DOI: 10.3389/fpubh.2024.1301421.

Rahmawati, T; Hsieh, H.-M.; Liang, F.-W. (2024): Inequalities in women's health insurance coverage before and after the implementation of universal health insurance in Indonesia. In *01975897* 45 (2). DOI: 10.1057/s41271-024-00480-7.

Raj, Anita (2011): Gender equity and universal health coverage in India. In *Lancet (London, England)* 377 (9766), pp. 618–619. DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(10)62112-5.

RamPrakash, R; Lakshmi, L (2018): Publicly Funded Health Insurance Schemes (PFHIS): A Systematic and Interpretive Review of Studies. Does Gender Equity Matter? In *eSocialSciences & Humanities*.

RamPrakash, R; Lingam, L (2021): Why is women's utilization of a publicly funded health insurance low?: a qualitative study in Tamil Nadu, India. In *BMC public health* 21 (1), p. 350. DOI: 10.1186/s12889-021-10352-4.

Ravindran, T.K.S. (2011): Reclaiming and Redefining Rights: Pathways to Universal Access to Reproductive Health Care in Asia.

Ravindran, T.K.S. (2012): Universal access: making health systems work for women. In *BMC public health* 12 Suppl 1 (Suppl 1), S4. DOI: 10.1186/1471-2458-12-S1-S4.

Ravindran, T.K.S.; Gaitonde, R. (2018): Health Inequities in India: A synthesis of Recent Evidence: Springer Singapore.

Ravindran, T.K.S.; Govender, V (2020): Sexual and reproductive health services in universal health coverage: a review of recent evidence from low- and middle-income countries. In *Sexual and reproductive health matters* 28 (2), p. 1779632. DOI: 10.1080/26410397.2020.1779632.

Remme, Michelle; Vassall, Anna; Fernando, Gabriela; Bloom, David E. (2020): Investing in the health of girls and women: a best buy for sustainable development. In *The BMJ* 369. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.m1175.

Rodin, Judith (2013): Accelerating action towards universal health coverage by applying a gender lens. In *Bulletin of the World Health Organization* 91 (9), pp. 710–711. DOI: 10.2471/BLT.13.127027.

Rycroft-Malone, Jo; McCormack, Brendan; Hutchinson, Alison M.; DeCorby, Kara; Bucknall, Tracey K.; Kent, Bridie et al. (2012): Realist synthesis: illustrating the method for implementation research. In *Implementation science* : IS 7 (1), p. 33. DOI: 10.1186/1748-5908-7-33.

Sciortino, Rosalia (2023): Aiming for a gender-transformative UHC agenda in Indonesia. In *Gender, Technology and Development* 27 (1), pp. 22–41. DOI: 10.1080/09718524.2022.2110151.

Sen, Gina; Govender, Veloshnee; El-Gamal, Salma (2021): Universal health coverage, gender equality and social protection: A health systems approach. A Health Systems Approach. United Nations Women.

Sen, Gita; Govender, Veloshnee; El-Gamal, Salma (2018): Universal health coverage, gender equality and social protection: A health systems approach. United Nation Women. New York. Available online at <https://dawnnet.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/sen-gbackground-paperdraftegmspsbp2.pdf>.

Sen, Gita; Östlin, Pirooska; George, Asha (2007): Unequal, Unfair, Ineffective and Inefficient: Gender inequity in health; Why it exists and how we can change it. Indian Institute of Management Bangalore; Karolinska Institutet. Available online at <https://repository.iimb.ac.in/handle/2074/13700>.

Serván-Mori, Edson; Cerecero-García, Diego; Heredia-Pi, Ileana B.; Pineda-Antúnez, Carlos; Sosa-Rubí, Sandra G.; Nigenda, Gustavo (2019): Improving the effective maternal-child health care coverage through synergies between supply and demand-side interventions: evidence from Mexico. In *Journal of Global Health* 9 (2), p. 20433. DOI: 10.7189/jogh.09.020433.

Serván-Mori, Edson; Orozco-Núñez, Emanuel; Heredia-Pi, Ileana; Armenta-Paulino, Nancy; Wirtz, Veronika J.; Meneses-Navarro, Sergio; Nigenda, Gustavo (2021): Public health insurance and ethnic disparities in maternal

health care: the case of vulnerable Mexican women over the last 25 years. In *Health Policy Plan* 36 (10), pp. 1671–1680. DOI: 10.1093/heapol/czab119.

Shaikh M; Peters SAE; Woodward M; Norton R; Jha V (2018): Sex differences in utilisation of hospital care in a state-sponsored health insurance programme providing access to free services in South India. In *BMJ global health* 3 (3), e000859. DOI: 10.1136/bmjgh-2018-000859.

Shao, Liming; Wang, Yiting; Wang, Xuhui; Ji, Lu; Huang, Rui (2022): Factors associated with health insurance ownership among women of reproductive age: A multicountry study in sub-Saharan Africa. In *19326203* 17 (4), e0264377. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0264377.

Sharma, SK; Nambiar D; Sankar H; Joseph J; Surendran S; Benny G (2023): Gender-specific inequalities in coverage of Publicly Funded Health Insurance Schemes in Southern States of India: evidence from National Family Health Surveys. In *BMC public health* 23 (1), p. 2414. DOI: 10.1186/s12889-023-17231-0.

Starrs, Ann M.; Ezeh, Alex; Barker, Gary; Basu, Alaka Malwade; Bertrand, Jane T.; Blum, Robert W. et al. (2018): Accelerate progress—sexual and reproductive health and rights for all: report of the Guttmacher–Lancet Commission. In *Lancet (London, England)* 391 (10140), pp. 2642–2692. DOI: 10.1016/s0140-6736(18)30293-9.

Tangcharoensathien V.; Patcharanarumol W.; Ir P.; Aljunid S.M.; Mukti A.G.; Akkhavong K. et al. (2011): Health-financing reforms in southeast Asia: Challenges in achieving universal coverage. In *01406736* 377 (9768). DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(10)61890-9.

The World Bank (2011): World Development Report 2012. Gender Equality and Development. Available online at <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/492221468136792185/pdf/Main-report.pdf>.

The World Bank (2019): High-Performance Health Financing for Universal Health Coverage. Driving Sustainable, Inclusive Growth in the 21st Century. The World Bank.

Third Annual UHC Financing Forum (2018): Equity on the Path to UHC: Deliberate Decisions for Fair Financing. Background Report. Washington DC. Available online at <https://www.worldbank.org/en/events/2017/10/20/third-annual-universal-health-coverage-financing-forum>.

UHC2030 (2020): State of commitment to universal health coverage: synthesis, 2020. Available online at https://www.uhc2030.org/fileadmin/uploads/uhc2030/2_What_we_do/2.1_Elevating_voices/2.1.4_State_of_UHC_Commitment/2020/SoUHCC_synthesis_2020_final_web.pdf.

UN General Assembly (2015): Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. A/RES/70/1.

UN General Assembly (2019): Political Declaration of the High-level Meeting on Universal Health Coverage “Universal health coverage: moving together to build a healthier world”.

United Nations (2024): Gender Inequality Index (United Nations). Available online at <https://hdr.undp.org/data-center/thematic-composite-indices/gender-inequality-index#/indicies/GII>.

United Nations Population Fund (2009): Concurrent Assessment of Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) in Selected States. Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Orissa, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh. United Nations Population Fund. New Delhi.

USAID (2014): Gender Analysis for USAID/Rwanda. Community Health and Improved Nutrition (CHAIN) Project. USAID. Available online at <https://2017-2020.usaid.gov/sites/default/files/documents/1860/GA%20-%20CHAIN%20project%20-%20FINAL%20Aug%2011%202014%20-%20Public%20Version.pdf>, checked on 10/23/2024.

Ved, R.; Scott, K.; Gupta, G.; Ummer, O.; Singh, S.; Srivastava, A.; George, A. S. (2019): How are gender inequalities facing India's one million ASHAs being

addressed? Policy origins and adaptations for the world's largest all-female community health worker programme. In *Hum Resour Health* 17 (1), p. 3. DOI: 10.1186/s12960-018-0338-0.

Vijayasingham, Lavanya; Govender, Veloshnee; Witter, Sophie; Remme, Michelle (2020): Employment based health financing does not support gender equity in universal health coverage. In *The BMJ* 371. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.m3384.

Witter, S; Ensor, T (op. 2012): Financing maternity care. In Julia Hussein, Affette McCaw-Binns, Roger Webber (Eds.): *Maternal and perinatal health in developing countries*. Wallingford, Oxfordshire, Cambridge, MA: CABI (CABI Books), pp. 77–95.

Witter, S; Somanathan, A (2012): Demand-Side Financing for Sexual and Reproductive Health Services in Low and Middle-Income Countries: A Review of the Evidence.

Witter, S.; Govender, V.; Ravindran, T.K.S.; Yates, R. (2017): Minding the gaps: health financing, universal health coverage and gender. In *Health policy and planning* 32 (suppl_5), v4-v12. DOI: 10.1093/heapol/czx063.

Witter S.; Boukhalifa C.; Cresswell J.A.; Daou Z.; Filippi V.; Ganaba R. et al. (2016): Cost and impact of policies to remove and reduce fees for obstetric care in Benin, Burkina Faso, Mali and Morocco. In *14759276* 15 (1). DOI: 10.1186/s12939-016-0412-y.

World Bank (2007): *Good Practice in Health Financing. Lessons from Reforms in Low and Middle Income Countries*. World Bank. Available online at https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/857381468120536506/pdf/733500WP0good000Box371944B00PUBLIC0.pdf?_gl=1*19irbc*_gcl_au*MTE4NzAyNTA4Ni4xNzI2Mjl2NDYz, checked on 9/13/2024.

World Bank (2016): *A Model from Mexico for the World*. World Bank. Available online at <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/feature/2014/11/19/un-modelo-de-mexico-para-el-mundo>, updated on 8/30/2016, checked on 10/18/2024.

World Bank (2024a): *Out-of-pocket expenditure (% of current health expenditure) - Thailand*. World Bank. World Bank Databank. Available online at

<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SH.XPD.OOPC.CH.ZS?locations=TH>, updated on 10/14/2024, checked on 10/14/2024.

World Bank (2024b): Out-of-pocket expenditure (% of current health expenditure) - Mexico. World Bank Databank. Available online at <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SH.XPD.OOPC.CH.ZS?locations=MX>, updated on 10/22/2024, checked on 10/22/2024.

World Bank (2024c): Out-of-pocket expenditure (% of current health expenditure) - India. World Bank. World Bank Databank. Available online at <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SH.XPD.OOPC.CH.ZS?locations=IN>, updated on 10/24/2024, checked on 10/24/2024.

World Economic Forum; McKinsey Health Institute (2024): Closing the Women's Health Gap: A \$1 Trillion Opportunity to Improve Lives and Economies. World Economic Forum. Geneva.

World Health Organization (2000): The World Health Report 2000. World Health Organization. Available online at <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/924156198X>, checked on 9/23/2024.

World Health Organization (2005): World Health Assembly Resolution 58.33. Geneva. Available online at https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/health-financing/sustainable-health-financing-universal-coverage-and-social-health-insurance.pdf?sfvrsn=f8358323_3.

World Health Organization (2009): Women and health. Today's evidence, tomorrow's agenda. Switzerland.

World Health Organization (2010a): Gender, women and primary health care renewal. A discussion paper. World Health Organization. Geneva. Available online at <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/44430>.

World Health Organization (2010b): Monitoring the building blocks of health systems: a handbook of indicators and their measurement strategies. Geneva.

World Health Organization (2010c): The World Health Report. Health Systems Financing: The Path of Universal Coverage. Geneva: World Health Organization.

World Health Organization (2020): Global strategy to accelerate the elimination of cervical cancer as a public health problem. Geneva.

World Health Organization (2021): Voice, agency, empowerment - handbook on social participation for universal health coverage. World Health Organization. Geneva. Available online at <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240027794>, checked on 10/28/2024.

World Health Organization (2024a): Thailand: Gender and Health. Available online at <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/344697/GER-Thailand-eng.pdf>, checked on 10/14/2024.

World Health Organization (2024b): Social participation for universal health coverage, health and well-being. WHA77 Resolution A77/A/CONF./3., checked on 10/28/2024.

World Health Organization; World Bank (2023): Tracking Universal Health Coverage: 2023 Global Monitoring Report: World Bank. Available online at <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/entities/publication/1ced1b12-896e-49f1-ab6f-f1a95325f39b>.

Yazbeck, Abdo S.; Savedoff, William D.; Hsiao, William C.; Kutzin, Joe; Soucat, Agnès; Tandon, Ajay et al. (2020): The Case Against Labor-Tax-Financed Social Health Insurance For Low- And Low-Middle-Income Countries. In *Health affairs (Project Hope)* 39 (5), pp. 892–897. DOI: 10.1377/hlthaff.2019.00874.

Ziegler, Susanne; Srivastava, Swati; Parmar, Divya; Basu, Sharmishtha; Jain, Nishant; Allegri, Manuela de (2024): A step closer towards achieving universal health coverage: the role of gender in enrolment in health insurance in India. In *BMC health services research* 24 (1), p. 141. DOI: 10.1186/s12913-023-10473-z.